

SATISFACTORY

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SatisFactory Common Information Data Exchange Model

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
3D	Three Dimensional
ADL	Advanced Distributed Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ARML	Augmented Reality Markup Language
B2MML	Business To Manufacturing Markup Language
CIDEM	Common Information Data Exchange Model
CIM	Common Information Model
COTS	Commercial Off The Shelf
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
DoW	Description of Work
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
gbXML	Green Building XML
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
I/O	Input/Output
KML	Keyhole Markup Language
LMS	Learning Management System
MESA	Manufacturing Enterprise Solutions Association
OGI	Oil and Gas Interoperability

O&M	Operations and Maintenance
POI	Point of Interest
SCORM	Sharable Content Object Reference Model
WP	Workpackage
XML	EXtensible Markup Language
XSD	XML Schema Definition

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In order for the SatisFactory project to fulfil its mission as a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem, it must cope with challenges represented by an information rich dynamic environment it is expected to operate within. Many separate heterogeneous and distributed information sources produce data continuously on different levels (including physical data from sensors) and granularities which should be processed in real-time as well as historical fashions. The information should be transformed, integrated, aggregated and stored in order to be understandable and accessible for all SatisFactory components that need it to support their operation.

The presented deliverable represents results of Task T1.4. More specifically, it defines Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM). The aim of CIDEM is to provide a model of information elements (e.g. concepts, even, relations, interfaces) used for information exchange between components as well as for modelling work performed by other tasks (e.g. knowledge models to support human resources optimization in T2.2). The CIDEM definition is considered as a shared vocabulary that enables to address the information needs for the SatisFactory framework components.

The work presented in the deliverable was based on a two-phase methodology approach. The first phase aimed at sources “external” to the project. The focus was on the identification on those standards which could be relevant for SatisFactory concept. The information models from these standards were analysed as a possible basis for CIDEM. The second phase (composed from six steps) reflected the evolution of the SatisFactory architecture. The requirements from SatisFactory components on storage services were the basis for the definition of CIDEM. Overall, the employed methodology followed a component-centric approach and this approach is reflected by this deliverable as well.

In order to reflect evolving SatisFactory architecture, several architecture parts/components’ requirements were specified (in form of interface specifications) and analysed. All components of the architecture have been considered:

- Smart Sensor Network;
- Middleware;
- Semantic Context Manager;
- Collaborative Tools;
- Integrated DSS;
- AR In-Factory Platform;
- Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence;
- Training/ Educational Platform;
- Multi-Modal & Augmented HMLs and AR Devices.

The requirements of these components have been analysed from the point of their data models, interfaces and their methods, as well as their impact on CIDEM (represented by the CIDEM component within the architecture).

Subsequently, based on the analysis, elements of CIDEM have been defined. They were defined for all those components that intend to interact with the CIDEM API. The definition of CIDEM has been produced in the form of CIDEM interfaces and XSD schemas (both

informal graphical visualisation as well as extensive formal definitions of elements and complex types are provided).

The presented deliverable reflects the current state of SatisFactory CIDEM as it is. Although the task devoted to the development of CIDEM finishes, this actual form of CIDEM is not guaranteed to be final, since there are other tasks running which may impact the CIDEM and induce its modifications in next project period. These modifications are going to be implemented and included in the CIDEM definition during the next iterations of the Task.

1. INTRODUCTION

The SatisFactory Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) will define the high level domain model comprising the basic elements (events, relations, interfaces etc.) underlying the SatisFactory collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem [1].

CIDEM in computing is open standard that defines how managed elements in an IT environment are represented as a common set of objects and relationships between them [2]. CIDEM specification consists of architecture and concepts of CIDEM, language (by which the CIDEM schema is defined), and a method for mapping CIDEM to other information models. The CIDEM architecture is usually object-oriented. The CIDEM elements are typically represented as classes and any relationships between them are represented as CIDEM associations. Inheritance allows specialization of common base elements into more specific derived elements. The CIDEM schema is conceptual schema which defines the specific set of objects and relationships between them that represent a common base for the managed elements in an IT environment.

The SatisFactory CIDEM is specified by the inputs/outputs interfaces between SatisFactory components and the Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM – serving as repository). This specification is formalized by signatures of CIDEM services (APIs) and XSD schemas defining data types used in services needed by SatisFactory components.

1.1 SCOPE OF THE REPORT

In general, the SatisFactory CIDEM is a standard that defines common set of SatisFactory specific data objects and relationship between them. The CIDEM specification is formalized as semantic model (conceptual schema) including all information which is needed by SatisFactory components, data structures, description of data storages meta-data (i.e. which information is stored where, what does the stored information contain, the information format, etc.). SatisFactory CIDEM serves as a vocabulary in communication between any components of the SatisFactory framework and the Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) API. The scope of SatisFactory CIDEM is to provide information and semantic model for the domain objects used by the SatisFactory components. Based on the description of these components from the SatisFactory report D2.1 (preliminary version) here is the outline of these objects:

- Shop-Floor information (static data)
 - Building information (geometry, etc.)
 - Assets information
 - Actors information
 - Procedures information
 - AR models
- Events and RAW data (dynamic data)
 - Measurements/ RAW data
 - Alarm events
 - Maintenance events

- Re-Adaptation events
- AR events
- Training events
- Social communication data (dynamic data)
 - Social communication events
- Gamification data (dynamic data)
 - Gamification events
- Units (static data)
 - Units for measurement and events

The domain objects are described by static data or by dynamic data. The static data (e.g. data about building structure, profiles of equipment etc.) will serve for interpretation of dynamic data (i.e. the RAW/Event data about an assembly line in a given building in a given time). The SatisFactory CIDEM enables to combine such dynamic data and static data. CIDEM process requests from the SatisFactory framework components (the requests are based on CIDEM specification) and store data in the hybrid repository. The response to these requests are serialised (based on CIDEM) and send over the CIDEM exporting services (APIs) to the requesting SatisFactory component.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The presented deliverable is structured and organised in the following chapters:

- **Section 2** presents a methodological approach employed to organise activities aiming at the specification of SatisFactory CIDEM. A two-phase methodology based on component-centric approach is introduced.
- **Section 3** identifies analyses relevant industrial standards, focusing on standards related to Common Information Models in factories.
- **Section 4** provides analysis of CIDEM requirements.
- **Section 5** specifies elements of CIDEM. The definitions have the form of CIDEM interfaces and formal XSD schemas.
- **Annex I** presents detailed extensive definitions of XSD elements and complex types. The definitions have a formal character.

2. METHODOLOGY

The SatisFactory Common Information Model is designed with the aim to be able to deal with a large amount of real-time information continuously acquired from several heterogeneous sources. According to DoW [1], the initial idea of the CIDEM was to:

- enable to translate information in heterogeneous formats into a format understandable to all SatisFactory components;
- describe information sources using the vocabulary that is used by all the SatisFactory components;
- define a format that will be accepted and used by all the project partners for straightforward translation from specification to the implementation phase.

The methodological approach provides a guideline for deriving information requirements that need to be reflected in the CIDEM and ensuring that the above mentioned points are properly reflected at the design of CIDEM. At first, activities were divided into two phases:

- **Phase 1: Analysis of relevant approaches and standards**

In the first phase of T1.4, there were naturally no requirements from the component developers, since initial specification of architecture was under development and was not stabilised yet. Therefore, the attention was aimed at literature. It aims to identify industry standards that could bring possible invigorating inspiration were identified. The identified industry standards were then analysed with similar intention as employed in case of identified projects. The results from both analyses were then documented as it can be seen in this deliverable.

- **Phase 2: SatisFactory requirements analysis**

In the second phase of T1.4 the activities were aimed at the evolving SatisFactory architecture. The methodology adopted during this phase is presented in the Figure 1. The focus was on components of the architecture that are relevant to the CIDEM – the components that need to interact with the central data repository represented by the CIDEM component. The employed methodology is therefore based on component centric approach (in opposition to sometimes used data centric approach).

Figure 1: Steps of the methodology adopted during SatisFactory requirement analysis (Phase 2)

The methodology adopted during Phase 2 (Figure 1), is divided into six steps, which are described below:

- **Step 1:** Analysis of SatisFactory architecture

The main goal of these activities was to clearly define the role of the SatisFactory CIDEM in the architecture as a common shared vocabulary. The vocabulary enables to access at data (both in read and write directions) in a unified way. The data access service is based on the vocabulary – the service itself is provided by the Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) API.

- **Step 2: Identification of relevant components**

Different architecture components have different needs for data to be consumed or produced by these components. Thus, all the defined components were analysed from the point of view of their data flow requirements in order to identify those Satisfactory components that could benefit from using the CIDEM API to store in and retrieve data from. The data flow was investigated according to Satisfactory architecture. The description of Satisfactory components contains part about dependencies with other components and brief description of component I/O interfaces. All of these descriptions were used for the identification of relevant components in this step.

- **Step 3: Description of component's interfaces**

After having identified an initial list of components utilising the CIDEM, the partners responsible for the development of the identified component were requested to define the specification of interfaces enabling storing data to or retrieving data from the CIDEM. Table 1 was used for the description of component's interfaces. The specification of the interfaces can be found in Section 5.

Table 1: Specification of component's interfaces

Method name (import/export)	Attributes	Type	Description

- **Step 4: Description of data types**

It is expected that specified interfaces use many calling parameters as well as returning parameters that are of Satisfactory specific data types. These data types were also specified by developers of the investigated components. Table 2 was used for the description of data types. The specification of the data types can be found in Section 4.

Table 2: Specification of Satisfactory types

Type name	Attributes	Type	Description

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- **Step 5: Analysis of descriptions**

Specifications of interfaces and data types used in the interfaces formed the main input into the analysis of requirements. Thus, this analysis followed a component centric approach. For each investigated component the specification of its interfaces were analysed and the respective interfaces of the CIDEM API, that will serve component's interfaces, were defined (if the interface is analogous to the interface of the component, e.g. an importing interface of a component is reflected as an exporting interface of CIDEM, it is called a mirroring interface). If the analysis of generated descriptions revealed that something is missing in them it was necessary to go back to Step 3 or Step 4 in the methodology. The analysis of requirements can be found in Section 4.

- **Step 6: Proposal of Common Information Model**

- **Step 6.1: Signatures of the interfaces**

By processing all the component interfaces of the CIDEM component, their names and signature are defined. These specifications of the CIDEM interfaces enable to read/store data for those SatisFactory components that need data access. The signatures of the interfaces are the first part of the common information model. The signatures of the interfaces can be found in Section 5.

- **Step 6.2: XSD specification of data types**

The next step was the analysis of the data types used in the interfaces. Thus, specifications of the calling and returning attributes were analysed. For each component one or more specific data types were proposed. This specification has to define data type and at the same time it has to be easily deployable during the development phase by all SatisFactory components. Since all the component developers agreed to use data in XML format in their interfaces and since the most suitable specification of the data types for XML data are XML schemas, the XML schemas were defined to specify the SatisFactory data types. The XSD specifications can be found in Section 5.

The signatures of the interfaces with the known XSD specification of the data types used in them enable to formally Access any SatisFactory specific data. To be able to provide such data to the requesting component over such interface or to be able to store them, the data have to be seamlessly and quickly handled and combined in the CIDEM.

In case the process of CIDEM definition revealed that something is missing, it was necessary to go back to Step 3 or Step 4 in the methodology.

Note, since the SatisFactory modelling activities are not closed yet, it is not the aim of this methodology to cover complete dependencies between stored information in the CIDEM and requested information from CIDEM.

3. EXISTING STANDARDS ANALYSIS

This section presents some industry standards. These standards were analysed before the requirements from SatisFactory components were specified (i.e. during phase 1 according to adopted methodology). Various standards were chosen in cooperation with project consortium and analysed during this period.

3.1 BUSINESS TO MANUFACTURING MARKUP LANGUAGE (B2MML)

B2MML or *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language* is an XML implementation of the ANSI/ISA-95, Enterprise-Control System Integration, family of standards (ISA-95), known internationally as IEC/ISO 62264. B2MML consists of a set of XML schemas written using the World Wide Web Consortium's XML Schema language (XSD) that implement the data models in the ISA-95 standard

B2MML is meant to be a common data definition to link ERP and supply chain management systems with manufacturing systems such as Industrial Control Systems and Manufacturing Execution Systems. B2MML is a complete implementation of ISA-95 and is published by the Manufacturing Enterprise Solutions Association (MESA).

B2MML covers the core package of a CIM. Data types from the domain of manufacturing, namely Assets, Equipment, Actors, Procedures, Measurements, Alerts and Re-Adaptation activities have been used and adapted to the SatisFactory CIDEM.

3.2 MIMOSA

MIMOSA is a non-profit 501(c)6 industry association, focused on enabling industry solutions leveraging supplier neutral, open standards, to establish an interoperable industrial ecosystem for Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) solutions components provided by major industry suppliers. In order to accomplish this goal, MIMOSA (working in cooperation with other like minded groups) has facilitated the development of the Oil and Gas Interoperability (OGI) Solutions Process, which includes the OGI Pilot, the OGI Solutions Architecture and the ISO OGI Technical Specification. Collectively, these elements establish the basis for the OGI Ecosystem, which is a true supplier neutral solutions environment enabling a major paradigm shift towards a solutions process providing lower cost, faster implementations and improved quality.

The OGI Solutions Process is driven by high value added industry use cases, developed, validated and managed by MIMOSA and industry partners. Current use cases span the full life-cycle of major classes of physical assets (plants, platforms and facilities) including true life-cycle management for the "digital asset" which must accurately reflect the physical assets being modeled, monitored and managed. The OGI Solutions Process leverages a portfolio of published international and industry standards and specifications, which are incorporated by reference into the various applicable use cases. Key standards in the portfolio include those associated with the OpenO&M Initiative (ISA 88/95, MIMOSA CCOM, OPC UA, OAGi BOD

architecture and OpenO&M ws-ISBM/CIR), as well as ISO 15926. The OGI Solutions Process seeks to avoid “re-inventing wheels” by leveraging a portfolio of existing standards purpose built for specific functions, with a focus on solving the business problems defined by the use cases, rather than on developing new standards. While a core team of owner/operators from the Oil and Gas industry were the initial stakeholders in this process, many of the use cases, standards, specifications and methods are applicable to a much broader cross section of industry sectors sometimes referred to as critical infrastructure. This is reflected in the breadth of industries represented by those contributing to or observing the OGI Pilot.

The OGI Pilot provides an industrial scale environment for use case development and improvement as well as establishing the proving grounds for interoperability within the OGI Ecosystem, which it defines based on the OGI Solutions Architecture. The OGI Pilot uses engineering data sets developed and managed by established industry EPC firms to be representative of the data sets required for real capital projects. These data sets are used as the basis for a “Continuous Handover”, where topological, schematic and parametric data sets are managed through simulated capital projects, then shared, exchanged and handed over at appropriate times (defined by the use cases) in machine readable, supplier neutral formats based on the portfolio of included standards. This “Digital Asset” is then used to directly provision the major classes of Operations and Maintenance (O&M) systems in a synchronized fashion, establishing the basis for the O&M systems to participate in defined O&M use cases. Collectively, the set of use cases and the portfolio of standards and specifications which they leverage, defines the basis for an “Industry Foundation Architecture”, which we now define as the OGI Solutions Architecture, upon which owner/operator specific business processes can be established through standardized methods for orchestration and governance.

In general, enterprises that are critically dependent upon complex physical assets have historically focused integration efforts on two major horizontal layers; Real-Time Control and Business Information Systems. Experts within these two areas seldom work directly with each other and do not focus on integration between the layers, which has resulted in a significant vertical information gap. This gap is compounded when O&M processes, systems and people are not efficiently integrated with each other, resulting in a corresponding horizontal information gap. Together, these gaps create an empty space in the very center of enterprise process and information integration.

In the past, operational inefficiencies coming from the lack of integration have been overlooked or minimized due to a general lack of interdisciplinary understanding. Overall optimization requires proper integration of O&M processes, systems and people. MIMOSA is working on effective solutions to eliminate these impediments to efficiency.

Historically, the O&M community has also lacked tight alignment with the Life-cycle Engineering community. This has led to a series of poorly connected activities with highly suboptimal results including data quality problems and the loss of configuration control for complex physical assets including plants, platforms and facilities. The effect has been a loss of integrity management for the digital asset which makes integrity management for the physical asset much more difficult. Working in close cooperation with groups such as POSC Caesar Association and Fiotech, MIMOSA is helping to establish the basis for a more integrated approach to Critical Infrastructure Management, holistically combining full life-cycle engineering with O&M activities. This supports more sustainable approaches to both integrity management and risk management.

MIMOSA covers the maintenance package of a CIM. Data types from the domain of manufacturing related to maintenance activities have been used and adapted to the SatisFactory CIDEM.

3.3 ARML

ARML (Augmented Reality Markup Language) is a descriptive, XML based data format, specifically targeted for mobile Augmented Reality (AR) applications. ARML focuses on mapping georeferenced Points of Interest (POIs) and their metadata, as well as mapping data for the POI content providers publishing the POIs to the AR application. ARML was defined in late 2009 by the creators of the Wikitude World Browser to enable developers to create content for Augmented Reality Browsers. ARML combines concepts and functionality typically shared by AR Browser, reuses concepts defined in OGC's KML (Keyhole Markup Language) standard and is already used by hundreds of AR content developers around the world.

ARML v1.0 is fairly restrictive and focuses on functionality Wikitude required back in 2009. Thus, ARML v2.0, while still using ideas coming from ARML v1.0, is targeted to be a complete redesign of the v1.0 format, taking the evolution of the AR industry, as well as other concepts and ideas into account. It is not specifically required to build on top of the proposed ARML v1.0 format. ARML v2.0 is focused on the following topics:

- KML, ARML v1.0 and other comparable data formats are purely descriptive formats. ARML v2.0 allows dynamic parts to modify the properties defined in the descriptive part.
- Define a set of events a developer can react to and execute custom functionality on occurrence of such events.
- Extend the rather basic POI presentation options (visual representation) to a more sophisticated visualizations like 3D objects, lines and polygons etc. Most likely, the geometry model of KML will be reused to represent POI geometries.
- Conceptual, it provides connecting ports to other widely used AR tracking methods (mainly visual tracking, but also audio tracking etc.). However, standardize tracking is not part of ARML v2.0 as such.

The ultimate goal of ARML v2.0 is to provide an extensible standard and framework for AR applications to serve the AR use cases currently used or developed. With AR, many different standards and computational areas developed in different working groups come together. ARML v2.0 needs to be flexible enough to tie into other standards without actually having to adopt them, thus creating an AR-specific standard with connecting points to other widely used and AR-relevant standards.

ARML covers the package of a model which is related to the augmented reality issues within SatisFactory project. Data types from the domain of augmented reality have been used and adapted to the SatisFactory CIDEM.

3.4 SCORM

Sharable Content Object Reference Model (SCORM) is a collection of standards and specifications for web-based electronic educational technology. It defines communications between client side content and a host system (called “the run-time environment”), which is commonly supported by a training management system. SCORM also defines how content may be packaged into a transferable format.

SCORM is a specification of the Advanced Distributed Learning (ADL) Initiative from the Office of the United States Secretary of Defense.

SCORM 2004 introduced a complex idea called sequencing, which is a set of rules that specifies the order in which a learner may experience content objects. In simple terms, they constrain a learner to a fixed set of paths through the training material, permit the learner to “bookmark” their progress when taking breaks, and assure the acceptability of test scores achieved by the learner. The standard uses XML, and it is based on the results of work done by AICC, IMS Global, IEEE, and Ariadne.

SCORM is the de facto industry standard for e-learning interoperability. Specifically, SCORM governs how online learning content and Learning Management Systems (LMSs) communicate with each other. SCORM does not speak to instructional design or any other pedagogical concern, it is purely a technical standard.

SCORM covers the package of the model which is related to the training activities within SatisFactory project. Data types from the domain of training have been used and adapted to the SatisFactory CIDEM.

3.5 GBXML

The *Green Building XML (gbXML)* schema, referred to as “gbXML”, was developed to facilitate the transfer of building information stored in CAD building information models, enabling integrated interoperability between building design models and a wide variety of engineering analysis tools and models available today. Today, gbXML has the industry support and wide adoption by the leading CAD vendors, Autodesk, Graphisoft, and Bentley. With the development of export and import capabilities in several major engineering modeling tools, gbXML has become a defacto industry standard schema. Its use dramatically streamlines the transfer of building information to and from engineering models, eliminating the need for time consuming plan take-offs. This removes a significant cost barrier to designing resource efficient buildings and specifying associated equipment. It enables building design teams to truly collaborate and realized the potential benefits of Building Information Modeling.

In June of 2000, the gbXML schema was submitted for inclusion in aecXML(TM), the industry-led initiative, launched by Bentley Systems with much excitement in the summer of 1999. Shortly thereafter, gbXML became the draft schema for the Building Performance & Analysis Working Group.

XML, extensible markup language, is a type of computer language that allows software programs to communicate information with little to no human interaction. This approach allows building designers to focus on what they want to do most - design beautiful,

environmentally responsible buildings that use intelligent technologies to meet their client's needs at the lowest cost possible. Helping realize the promise of Building Information Modeling, gbXML allows intelligent solutions for the design, certification, operation, maintenance, and recycling of buildings. The possibilities are limited only by the collective imagination of the building design community.

gbXML covers the package of a CIM which is related to the building (pilot area) description within SatisFactory project. Data types from the domain of building have been used and adapted to the SatisFactory CIDEM.

3.6 OPENSOCIAL

OpenSocial is a public specification that defines a set of APIs for social applications that run on the web. OpenSocial's goal is to make more apps available to more users, by providing a common API that can be used in many different contexts. Developers can create applications, using standard JavaScript and HTML, that run on social websites that have implemented the OpenSocial APIs. These websites, known as OpenSocial containers, allow developers to access their social information; in return they receive a large suite of applications for their users.

The OpenSocial APIs expose methods for accessing information about people, their friends, and their data, within the context of a container. This means that when running an application on Orkut, the user is interacting with Orkut friends, while running the same application on MySpace lets user interact with user's MySpace friends.

OpenSocial covers the package of the model which is related to the social communication activities within SatisFactory project. Data types from the domain of social platforms have been used and adapted to the SatisFactory CIDEM.

4. ANALYSIS OF CIDEM REQUIREMENTS

Analysis of CIDEM requirements is tightly connected with the requirements to the Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM) API, since CIDEM API provides the information backend for the interface. As it is described in D2.1 [3], all SatisFactory Components communicate among each other through the CIDEM API. Other modules that request information from the CIDEM or need to store information in the CIDEM will interact with this module. The CIDEM API will provide functionality for data access and management (import, export, search, access, etc.).

In following sections we try to identify possible data structures flowing between these components and the CIDEM. It was decided that the data structure specification in CIDEM will be based on XML schemas. One of the reasons for it is that XML schema is a (industry) standard for data structure specification in Middleware. The second reason is that the semantics of elements from these XML schemas (structural level of data) can be then quite straightforward defined in the ontologies (semantic level of data).

The design of CIDEM was mainly determined by the information required by the SatisFactory components that can be generated only as a combination (and/or modification) of particular information models.

The SatisFactory components requesting information from the CIDEM using the web services of CIDEM to retrieve or to save information to the CIDEM storage. Other modules are active in this case, and the CIDEM actively calls only the Ontology Module in case semantic resolution of queries is needed. For example, if event related to the space will be requested, events related to all the sensors and equipment within the space in selected time should be returned. All the web services will use a composition of different CIDEM elements for information exchange. The scenarios that incorporate CIDEM are described in Section 5.

Note that CIDEM will contain also original information in raw form that can be accessed through the references in CIDEM elements to them. Therefore these data could be also accessible by SatisFactory components. The elements described below are considered as shared vocabulary within the SatisFactory system.

4.1 INFORMATION MODEL

The shop-floor information model has to be imported into the CIDEM at the beginning of the pilots. It contains a lot of information that is not needed directly by SatisFactory components so it is proposed a simplified information model structure that will be parsed from the original model. The full shop-floor information representation of the factory will be also directly stored in XML, so it could be later used it for visualisation or exporting.

The SatisFactory information model is comprised by a number of different components, which are listed below:

- ShopFloor
- Equipment List
- Sensor/Devices List

- Assets List
- Actors List
- Procedures List
- Augmented Reality Model List

Each of these elements of the SatisFactory Information Model is analysed below.

4.1.1 ShopFloor

ShopFloor model has to be imported into the CIDEM at the beginning of each pilot. It contains all the static information about the geometry of the building (walls, windows, spaces, etc.), which will be used as a common base for all SatisFactory components. The location of all information will be in accordance to this ShopFloor model. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known open schema has been adopted, the *Green Building XML (gbXML)*. gbXML format is supported by almost all design tools, so it could be easily portable.

Properties that are filtered from the original ShopFloor Model are:

- Building, that contains spaces;
- Space IDs;
- Space area.

The basic concept for modeling the shop-floor in SatisFactory is a Space representing any chosen place in the building, usually one enclosed space surrounded by walls. A space contains equipment, assets, sensors etc.

The Shop-Floor model is going to be extended in building level, so as to be able to interconnected with other systems such as Energy Efficiency and Resource Management, where the multi-purpose aspect of Building Information Model (BIM) is going to very useful for the overall operation of the factory as a factory and as a building as well.

4.1.2 Equipment List

Equipment list is very important information concerning the pilots and the factory operation, which could be inserted to the CIDEM at the beginning of each pilot. It contains the information regarding the equipment that is located in the factory, and more specifically to the spaces/ areas where the use cases are going to be deployed. This information could be used by most of the SatisFactory components (such as maintenance tools and other subcomponents of the integrated Decision Support System (DSS), etc.). In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Equipment List are:

- Equipment IDs;
- Equipment list;
- Equipment in a specific space/location;
- Equipment of the same type.

The basic concept for modeling the equipment in shop-floor is the availability of all the information about the equipment in the shop-floor in general and more specifically in each space.

4.1.3 Sensors List

Sensor list contains information regarding the sensors that are already installed or will be installed within SatisFactory project in the shop-floor and provide information about the dynamic behaviour of the shop-floor (e.g. assembly lines, production lines, etc.). This information could be used by most of the SatisFactory components (such as maintenance tools and other subcomponents of the integrated Decision Support System (DSS), Augmented Reality tools, etc.). Although “Equipment List” described above could be used to this end, we preferred a more dedicated solution, which is inherited by Adapt4EE [4] and INERTIA [5] projects. This solution has been applied and efficiently tested in these two projects in real-life environments in their pilot sites.

Properties that are filtered from the Sensor List are:

- Sensor IDs;
- Sensor list;
- Sensors in a specific space/location;
- Sensors of the same type.

The basic concept for modeling the sensors in a shop-floor is the availability of the overall information about the sensor network in the shop-floor in general and more specifically in each space.

4.1.4 Assets List

Assets list is very important information concerning the pilots and the factory operation, which could be inserted to the CIDEM at the beginning of each pilot. It contains the information regarding the assets of the factory. In this category, information about assets that could not be categorized in “Equipment List” or belong to the general category of assets. This information could be used by most of the SatisFactory components (such as maintenance tools and other subcomponents of the integrated Decision Support System (DSS), Augmented Reality tools, etc.). In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Assets List are:

- Asset IDs;
- Asset list.

The basic concept for modeling the asset in shop-floor is the availability of useful information about the shop-floor and its assets.

4.1.5 Actors List

Actors list contains information regarding the actors that are involved in the use cases within SatisFactory project in the shop-floor. This information could be used by most of the SatisFactory components (such as maintenance tools and other subcomponents of the integrated Decision Support System (DSS), Augmented Reality tools, etc.) in conjunction with the Procedures that are described below. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Actors List are:

- Actor IDs;
- Actors list;
- Actors work in a specific space/location.

The basic concept for modeling the actors in a shop-floor is the availability of the information about the actors that work in each space/ location and in general in the shop-floor, and of course the kind of the job that each actor performs. This information will be available in conjunction with the Procedures/ Activities running in each shop-floor.

4.1.6 Procedures List

Procedures list contains information regarding the procedures/ activities that are occurring during the use cases within SatisFactory project in the shop-floor. This information could be used by most of the SatisFactory components, especially those that are related to the assembly and training activities (e.g. Augmented Reality tools, etc.), in conjunction with the Actors that are described above. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Procedures List are:

- Procedure IDs;
- Procedures list;
- Procedures performed in a specific space/location.

The basic concept for modeling the procedures in a shop-floor is the availability of the information about the procedures/ activities that performed in each space/ location and in general in the shop-floor, and of course the kind of the job that each actor performs. This information will be available in conjunction with the Actors employed in each shop-floor.

4.1.7 Augmented Reality Models List

Augmented Reality Models list contains information regarding the 2D and 3D models that are going to be utilized by the Augmented Reality tools during the SatisFactory use cases in the shop-floors. It is a useful information for all SatisFactory components related to Augmented Reality tools. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Augmented Reality Markup Language (ARML)*, which is used by many augmented reality tools and applications in the literature.

Properties that are filtered from the Augmented Reality Models are:

- AR model IDs;
- AR model list;
- AR model required for a specific procedure.

The basic concept for modeling the AR models in a shop-floor is the proper operation and performance of AR tools and solutions provided by SatisFactory project.

4.2 EVENTS

All the events and measurements extracted in a shop-floor have to be imported into the CIDEM dynamically during the pilot tests through the middleware component. They contain all the information about the dynamic behaviour and status of the shop-floor. This information is mainly collected by the sensors and systems installed in the shop-floor (including the already installed sensors and systems). Furthermore, information extracted by the SatisFactory components (e.g. maintenance events, incident events, etc.) will be stored to the CIDEM as well. This information is going to be directly stored in in the CIDEM in XML format through the CIDEM API, so it could be later used either for visualization or exporting.

The SatisFactory events could be categorized in a number of classes, which are listed below:

- Measurements;
- Alerts;
- Maintenance events;
- Re-adaptation events;
- Augmented reality events;
- Training events.

Each of these event categories of the SatisFactory is analysed below.

4.2.1 Measurements

Measurements have to be imported into the CIDEM during the pilot deployment and execution. They contain all the dynamic information regarding the shop-floor and its operation. The installed multi-sensorial network will feed the CIDEM through Middleware with all this information, which is vital for the correct operation of the SatisFactory components and will be utilized by all of them. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Measurements are:

- Measurement ID;
- Measurement description;
- Space where measurement has received;
- Measurement timestamp;
- Measurement value.

The basic concept for modelling the measurements of shop-floor in SatisFactory is that measurements represents the dynamic behaviour of the shop-floor.

4.2.2 Alerts

Alerts contain the dynamic information of a shop-floor related to incidents and other abnormal situations, captured by the SatisFactory components. The SatisFactory components will feed the CIDEM with this information, which is vital for the correct operation of the overall shop-floor. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Alerts are:

- Alert ID;
- Alert description;
- Space where alert has occurred;
- Alert timestamp.

The basic concept for modelling the alerts of shop-floor in SatisFactory is that they represent/ indicate abnormal situations in the workplace, whose timely solutions could eliminate accidents and improve the working environment.

4.2.3 Maintenance Events

Maintenance events contain the dynamic information of a shop-floor related to the maintenance issues of the equipment and the assets in the shop-floor. These issues are related with the scheduled maintenance, as well as with the maintenances that should occur immediately after an event (e.g. an incident, etc.). The SatisFactory components will feed the CIDEM with this information, which is vital for the correct operation of the overall shop-floor, since the proper maintenance of the equipment is related to a number of very important issues, such as employees safety, production, etc. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *An Operations and Maintenance Information Open System Alliance (MIMOSA)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Maintenance Events are:

- Diagnosis ID;
- Diagnosis description;
- Reference asset/equipment;
- Recommendation ID;
- Recommendation description.

The basic concept for modelling the maintenance events of shop-floor in SatisFactory is that they are vital for the correct operation of the overall shop-floor improving employees' safety, increasing production, etc. Furthermore, proper scheduled maintenance could protect from potential incidents.

4.2.4 Re-adaptation Events

Re-adaptation events contain the dynamic information of a shop-floor related to the issues of production lines and reallocation of human resources at them. Information related to the

production lines and the human resources allocation will be dynamically analysed by the SatisFactory components, providing a better reallocation of the human resources so as to have the optimum performance and employees satisfaction. The SatisFactory components will feed the CIDEM with this information. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Business To Manufacturing Markup Language (B2MML)*, which is used by many factories and integrated systems in manufacturing environments.

Properties that are filtered from the Re-Adaptation events are:

- Re-Adaptation ID;
- Re-Adaptation description;
- Re-Adaptation location;
- Publication date;
- Duration.

The basic concept for modelling the re-adaptation events of shop-floor in SatisFactory is that the dynamic environment of a shop-floor needs potential re-adaptation of the human resources so as to achieve the optimum employees' satisfaction and production performance.

4.2.5 Augmented Reality Events

Augmented Reality (AR) events contain the dynamic information that is related to the AR activities by the SatisFactory components in the shop-floor. All these events should be stored to the CIDEM. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Augmented Reality Markup Language (ARML)*, which is used by many tools and application that are related with augmented reality.

Properties that are filtered from the Augmented Reality events are:

- Augmented Reality ID;
- Augmented Reality type;
- Event time;
- Event location;
- Object properties;
- Dynamic properties.

The basic concept for modelling the AR events occurred by the SatisFactory components in the shop-floor is the necessity of keeping historic records and the re-usage of AR models and their properties.

4.2.6 Training Events

Training events contain the dynamic information of a shop-floor related to the training activities performed by the SatisFactory components at the shop-floor. The information related to these issues will be dynamically stored to the CIDEM. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *Sharable Content Object Reference Model (SCORM)*, which is used by a large number of e-learning software products.

Properties that are filtered from the Training events are:

- Training event ID;
- Training event description;
- Trainer ID;
- Interactions;
- Training location;
- Training mode;
- Progress measure;
- Scores;
- Session times;
- Success status;
- Comments.

The basic concept for modelling the training events of shop-floor in SatisFactory is the dynamic form of the training events, which is depended on the trainer, the time, etc. All this information could provide useful information to the employees and the trainers increasing their productivity and their comprehension at the workflow.

4.3 SOCIAL COMMUNICATION

All the events and information related to the social communication that is going to be extracted and collected in the shop-floor by the corresponding SatisFactory components have to be imported into the CIDEM dynamically during the pilot tests through the middleware component in XML format through CIDEM API. They will contain important information about the communication among employees through the SatisFactory communication platform. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *OpenSocial standard*, which is used by a large number of social web working groups and products.

Properties that are filtered from the Social Communication information are:

- Event ID;
- Event type;
- Event time;
- Persons involved;
- Groups;
- Activities.

The basic concept for modelling the social communication events and information of the corresponding components of SatisFactory in the shop-floor is the historical records and the issue that all social communication platforms needs to keep records of every event and information is related to the communication activities within the platform.

4.4 GAMIFICATION

All the events and information related to the gamification activities within SatisFactory projects should be collected and stored dynamically in the CIDEM during the pilot tests through middleware component. The information about the gamification activities during

training process as well as during the normal activities of employees, which are going to be enriched with gamification techniques in order to increase the attractiveness of the specific processes and activities, is very important to be stored. In order to cope with SatisFactory needs, a well-known standard was adopted, the *SportsML-G2 standard*, which is used by a large number of products and applications the models sports and gamification processes.

Properties that are filtered from the Gamification information are:

- Event ID;
- Event type;
- Event time;
- Gamification statistics;
- Gamification actions;
- Gamification highlights;
- Awards.

The basic concept for modelling the gamification events and activities of the corresponding components of SatisFactory in the shop-floor is the historical records and the issue that all gamification tools needs to keep records of every event and information is related to the them.

4.5 ARCHITECTURE – CIDEM MAPPING

In this subsection, a brief mapping among CIDEM components and SatisFactory architecture components is presented.

Table 3: Architecture – CIDEM mapping

CIDEM component	Smart Sensor Network	Middleware	Semantic Context Manager	Collaborative Tools	Integrated DSS	AR In-Factory Platform	Operational Platform with Augmented Reality	Training Educational Platform	Multi-Modal & Augmented HMI's and AR Devices
ShopFloor Model	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Equipment Model		X	X	X	X		X	X	
Sensor Model	X	X	X		X				
Asset Model		X	X	X	X				
Actor Model		X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Procedure Model		X	X		X		X	X	
Measurements	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Alerts		X	X		X	X	X		X

SATISFACTORY

CIDEM component	Smart Sensor Network	Middleware	Semantic Context Manager	Collaborative Tools	Integrated DSS	AR In-Factory Platform	Operational Platform with Augmented Reality	Training Educational Platform	Multi-Modal & Augmented HMIs and AR Devices
Maintenance Events		X	X		X	X	X		
Re-Adaptation Events		X	X		X	X	X		
Augmented Reality Events		X	X			X	X		
Training Events		X	X	X		X		X	
Social Communication Model		X	X	X					
Gamification Model		X	X	X					

5. CIDEM SPECIFICATIONS

Based on the analysis from Section 4 the elements of CIDEM are defined here. These elements are defined for all SatisFactory components that are interacting with CIDEM through its APIs. The definition of CIDEM for each of such component consists of CIDEM interface name and XSD schemas defining data types used in these interfaces. Thus the structure of CIDEM description for each SatisFactory component looks as following:

- CIDEM interfaces
- XSD schemas

The CIDEM interfaces in many cases mirror the components interfaces. In these cases the names of CIDEM (mirroring) interfaces are provided, since the signature is analogous to the signatures of component interfaces. In the cases where specific CIDEM interfaces are defined the signatures are provided.

The full technical documentation to XSD schemas can be found in the Annex I.

A high level diagram of the CIDEM structure is illustrated at Figure 2. Each element of the schema is analysed below.

Figure 2: High level structure of the CIDEM

5.1 INFORMATION MODEL

The information model is comprised by the shop-floor static information. A high level schema is depicted at Figure 3. More details about its elements are in the following subsections.

Figure 3: High level structure of the Information Model

5.1.1 ShopFloor

5.1.1.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** `setShopFloorModel` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** gbXML)
- **boolean** `updateShopFloorModel` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** new_gbXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** `getShopFloorModel` (**string** shopFloorID)

5.1.1.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 4: ShopFloor Model schema

5.1.2 Equipment List

5.1.2.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

SATISFACTORY

- **boolean** **setEquipment** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** equipmentID, **string** equipmentXML)
- **boolean** **updateEquipment** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** equipmentID, **string** new_equipmentXML)
- **boolean** **setEquipmentList** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** equipmentID, **string** equipmentListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** **getEquipmentList** (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** **getEquipmentByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** equipmentID)
- **string** **getEquipmentByLocation** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** spaceID)

5.1.2.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 5: Equipment schema

5.1.3 Sensors List

5.1.3.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** **setSensor** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** sensorID, **string** sensorXML)
- **boolean** **updateSensor** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** sensorID, **string** new_sensorXML)
- **boolean** **setSensorList** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** sensorListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** **getSensorList** (**string** shopFloorID)

- `string getSensorNum (string shopFloorID)`
- `string getSensorInterfaces (string shopFloorID)`
- `string getSensorInterfaceByID (string shopFloorID, string sensorID)`
- `string getSensorAddresses (string shopFloorID)`
- `string getSensorAddressByID (string shopFloorID, string sensorID)`
- `string getSensorByID (string shopFloorID, string sensorID)`
- `string getSensorByLocation (string shopFloorID, string spaceID)`
- `string getSensorByType (string shopFloorID, string sensorType)`
- `string getSensorPacketLossByID (string shopFloorID, string sensorID)`
- `string getSensorPacketRateByID (string shopFloorID, string sensorID)`
- `string getSensorLatencyByID (string shopFloorID, string sensorID)`

5.1.3.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 6: Sensor schema

5.1.4 Assets List

5.1.4.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** **setAsset** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** assetID, **string** assetXML)
- **boolean** **updateAsset** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** assetID, **string** new_assetXML)
- **boolean** **setAssetList** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** assetListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** **getAssetList** (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** **getAssetByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** assetID)
- **string** **getAssetByDescription** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** assetDescription)

5.1.4.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 7: Asset schema

5.1.5 Actors List

5.1.5.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** **setActor** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** actorID, **string** actorXML)
- **boolean** **updateActor** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** actorID, **string** new_actorXML)
- **boolean** **setActorList** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** actorListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** **getActorList** (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** **getActorByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** actorID)

5.1.5.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 8: Actor schema

5.1.6 Procedures List

5.1.6.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** **setProcedure** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** procedureID, **string** procedureXML)
- **boolean** **updateProcedure** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** procedureID, **string** new_procedureXML)
- **boolean** **setProcedureList** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** procedureListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** **getProcedureList** (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** **getProcedureByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** procedureID)
- **string** **getProcedureByLocation** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** spaceID)

5.1.6.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 9: Procedure schema

5.1.7 Augmented Realist Models List

5.1.7.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** setARModel (string shopFloorID, string ARmodelID, string ARmodelXML)
- **boolean** updateARModel (string shopFloorID, string ARmodelID, string new_ARmodelXML)
- **boolean** setARModelList (string shopFloorID, string ARmodelListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** getARModelList (string shopFloorID)
- **string** getARModelByID (string shopFloorID, string ARmodelID)

5.1.7.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 10: Augmented Reality Model schema

5.2 EVENTS

The events model is comprised by the shop-floor dynamic information. A high level schema is depicted at Figure 11. More details about its elements are in the following subsections.

Figure 11: High level structure of the Events model

5.2.1 Measurements

5.2.1.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- `boolean setMeasurement (string shopFloorID, string measurementID, string measurementXML)`
- `boolean updateMeasurementByID (string shopFloorID, string measurementID, string new_measurementXML)`
- `boolean setMeasurementList (string shopFloorID, string measurementListXML)`

Exporting Interfaces

- `string getMeasurementList (string shopFloorID)`
- `string getMeasurementByID (string shopFloorID, string measurementID)`
- `string getMeasurementByType (string shopFloorID, string measurementType)`
- `string getMeasurementByTime (string shopFloorID, string measurementStartTime, string measurementEndTime)`
- `string getMeasurementBySpace (string shopFloorID, string spaceID)`
- `string getMeasurementByTimeSpace (string shopFloorID, string measurementStartTime, string measurementEndTime, string spaceID)`

5.2.1.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 12: Measurement schema

5.2.2 Alerts

5.2.2.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean setAlert** (string shopFloorID, string alertID, string alertXML)
- **boolean updateAlertByID** (string shopFloorID, string alertID, string new_alertXML)
- **boolean setAlertList** (string shopFloorID, string alertListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string getAlertList** (string shopFloorID)
- **string getAlertByID** (string shopFloorID, string alertID)
- **string getAlertByType** (string shopFloorID, string alertType)
- **string getAlertByTime** (string shopFloorID, string alertStartTime, string alertEndTime)
- **string getAlertBySpace** (string shopFloorID, string spaceID)
- **string getAlertByTimeSpace** (string shopFloorID, string alertStartTime, string alertEndTime, string spaceID)

5.2.2.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 13: Alerts schema

5.2.3 Maintenance Events

5.2.3.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** **setMaintenanceEventDiagnosis** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID, **string** maintenanceEventDiagnosisXML)
- **boolean** **setMaintenanceEventRecommendation** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID, **string** maintenanceEventRecommendationXML)
- **boolean** **updateMaintenanceEventDiagnosisByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID, **string** new_maintenanceEventDiagnosisXML)
- **boolean** **updateMaintenanceEventRecommendationByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID, **string** new_maintenanceEventRecommendationXML)
- **boolean** **setMaintenanceEventList**(**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID, **string** maintenanceEventListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** **getMaintenanceEventList** (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventDiagnosisByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventRecommendationByID** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventByType** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventType)

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- **string** **getMaintenanceEventDiagnosisByType** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventType)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventRecommendationByType** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventType)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventByTime** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventStartTime, **string** maintenanceEventEndTime)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventDiagnosisByTime** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventStartTime, **string** maintenanceEventEndTime)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventRecommendationByTime** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventStartTime, **string** maintenanceEventEndTime)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventBySpace** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** spaceID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventDiagnosisBySpace** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** spaceID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventRecommendationBySpace** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** spaceID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventByTimeSpace** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventStartTime, **string** maintenanceEventEndTime, **string** spaceID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventDiagnosisByTimeSpace** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventStartTime, **string** maintenanceEventEndTime, **string** spaceID)
- **string** **getMaintenanceEventRecommendationByTimeSpace** (**string** shopFloorID, **string** maintenanceEventStartTime, **string** maintenanceEventEndTime, **string** spaceID)

5.2.3.2 XSD Schemas

The screenshot shows a multi-layered XSD Schema editor interface. The top layer is 'SFEvents_Type' containing an 'EventList' sequence. The middle layer is 'Maintenance' containing a 'Diagnosis' sequence. The bottom layer shows the detailed elements of the 'Diagnosis' sequence, which are listed in a table format.

Element Name	Data Type
sg_prop_db_site	site_codeSimpleType
sg_prop_db_id	xsdunsignedInt
sg_prop_event_id	xsdunsignedInt
segment_site	site_codeSimpleType
segment_id	xsdunsignedInt
ev_db_site	site_codeSimpleType
ev_db_id	xsdunsignedInt
event_type_code	xsdunsignedInt
severity_lev_db_site	site_codeSimpleType
severity_lev_db_id	xsdunsignedInt
severity_lev_type_code	xsdunsignedInt
gmt_proposed	dateTimeWithoutTimezone
pr_loc_hr_delta	xsdshort
pr_loc_min_delta	xsdunsignedShort
by_org_site	site_codeSimpleType
by_agent_id	xsdunsignedInt
likelihood_prob	xsddouble
est_gmt_start	dateTimeWithoutTimezone
st_loc_hr_delta	xsdshort
st_loc_min_delta	xsdunsignedShort
est_gmt_occur_end	dateTimeWithoutTimezone
end_loc_hr_delta	xsdshort
end_loc_min_delta	xsdunsignedShort
ch_patt_db_site	site_codeSimpleType
ch_patt_db_id	xsdunsignedInt
ch_patt_type_code	xsdunsignedInt
user_tag_idcnt	varchar254
name	varchar254
gmt_audited	dateTimeWithoutTimezone
aud_loc_hr_delta	xsdshort
aud_loc_min_delta	xsdunsignedShort
aud_quality_code	xsdunsignedShort
aud_by_org_site	site_codeSimpleType
aud_by_agent_id	xsdunsignedInt
gmt_last_updated	dateTimeWithoutTimezone
last_upd_db_site	site_codeSimpleType
last_upd_db_id	xsdunsignedInt
rstat_type_code	xsdunsignedShort
linfo	linfo

Element Name	Data Type
segment_site	site_codeSimpleType
segment_id	xsdunsignedInt
gmt_recommendation	dateTimeWithoutTimezone
by_agent_site	site_codeSimpleType
by_agent_id	xsdunsignedInt
loc_hr_delta	xsdshort
loc_min_delta	xsdunsignedShort
priority_lev_db_site	site_codeSimpleType
priority_lev_db_id	xsdunsignedInt
priority_lev_type_code	xsdunsignedInt
user_tag_idcnt	varchar254
name	varchar254
gmt_last_updated	dateTimeWithoutTimezone
last_upd_db_site	site_codeSimpleType
last_upd_db_id	xsdunsignedInt
rstat_type_code	xsdunsignedShort
linfo	linfo

Figure 14: Maintenance schema

5.2.4 Re-Adaptation Events

5.2.4.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** `setReAdaptationEvent` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** readaptationEventID, **string** readaptationXML)
- **boolean** `updateReAdaptationEventByID` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** readaptationEventID, **string** new_readaptationXML)
- **boolean** `setReAdaptationEventList` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** readaptationListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** `getReAdaptationEventList` (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** `getReAdaptationEventByID` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** readaptationEventID)
- **string** `getReAdaptationEventByType` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** readaptationEventType)
- **string** `getReAdaptationEventByTime` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** readaptationEventStartTime, **string** readaptationEventEndTime)
- **string** `getReAdaptationEventBySpace` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** spaceID)
- **string** `getReAdaptationEventByTimeSpace` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** readaptationEventStartTime, **string** readaptationEventEndTime, **string** spaceID)

5.2.4.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 15: Re-Adaptation schema

5.2.5 Augmented Reality Events

5.2.5.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** setAREvent (string shopFloorID, string AREventID, string AREventXML)
- **boolean** updateAREventByID (string shopFloorID, string AREventID, string new_AREventXML)
- **boolean** setAREventList (string shopFloorID, string AREventListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** getAREventList (string shopFloorID)
- **string** getAREventByID (string shopFloorID, string AREventID)
- **string** getAREventByTime (string shopFloorID, string AREventStartTime, string AREventEndTime)
- **string** getAREventBySpace (string shopFloorID, string spaceID)
- **string** getAREventByTimeSpace (string shopFloorID, string AREventStartTime, string AREventEndTime, string spaceID)

5.2.5.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 16: Augmented Reality Events schema

5.2.6 Training Events

5.2.6.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** setTrainingEvent (string shopFloorID, string TrainingEventID, string TrainingEventXML)
- **boolean** updateTrainingEventByID (string shopFloorID, string TrainingEventID, string new_TrainingEventXML)

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- **boolean** `setTrainingEventList` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** TrainingEventListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** `getTrainingEventList` (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** `getTrainingEventByID` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** TrainingEventID)
- **string** `getTrainingEventByTime` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** TrainingEventStartTime, **string** TrainingEventEndTime)
- **string** `getTrainingEventByPerson` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** personID)
- **string** `getTrainingEventByTimePerson` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** TrainingEventStartTime, **string** TrainingEventEndTime, **string** personID)

5.2.6.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 17: Training Events schema

5.3 SOCIAL COMMUNICATION

5.3.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean** `setSocialCommunicationEvent` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommID, **string** socialCommXML)
- **boolean** `updateSocialCommunicationEventByID` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommID, **string** new_socialCommXML)
- **boolean** `setSocialCommunicationEventList` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string** `getSocialCommunicationEventList` (**string** shopFloorID)
- **string** `getSocialCommunicationEventByID` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommID)
- **string** `getSocialCommunicationEventByType` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommType)
- **string** `getSocialCommunicationEventByTime` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommStartTime, **string** socialCommEndTime)
- **string** `getSocialCommunicationEventByPerson` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** personID)
- **string** `getSocialCommunicationEventByTimeType` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommStartTime, **string** socialCommEndTime, **string** socialCommType)
- **string** `getSocialCommunicationEventByTimePerson` (**string** shopFloorID, **string** socialCommStartTime, **string** socialCommEndTime, **string** personID)

5.3.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 18: Social Communication Events schema

5.4 GAMIFICATION

5.4.1 Interfaces

Importing Interfaces

- **boolean setGamificationEvent** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationID, string gamificationXML)
- **boolean updateGamificationEventByID** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationID, string new_gamificationXML)
- **boolean setGamificationEventList** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationListXML)

Exporting Interfaces

- **string getGamificationEventList** (string shopFloorID)
- **string getGamificationEventByID** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationID)
- **string getGamificationEventByType** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationType)
- **string getGamificationEventByTime** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationStartTime, string gamificationEndTime)
- **string getGamificationEventByPerson** (string shopFloorID, string personID)
- **string getGamificationEventByTimeType** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationStartTime, string gamificationEndTime, string gamificationType)
- **string getGamificationEventByTimePerson** (string shopFloorID, string gamificationStartTime, string gamificationEndTime, string personID)

5.4.2 XSD Schemas

Figure 19: Gamification Events schema

6. TECHNOLOGIES USED FOR THE CIDEM AND CIDEM APIS

CIDEM is provided as a set of XSD schemas that define the structure of the model. For reusability and easier readability of the model, it is splitted into several parts. Every part of the CIDEM has its target namespace and a corresponding XSD source file:

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/CIDEM> (Satisfactory.xsd)

- Main file that can be used to validate XMLs.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/common> (Satisfactory-Common.xsd)

- Common elements of the CIDEM.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/gbXML> (gbXML_v5.12.xsd)

- ShopFloor model elements.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/B2MML> (B2MML.xsd)

- Equipment, Assets, Actors, Procedures, Measurements, Alerts, and Re-Adaptation elements.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/MIMOSA> (MIMOSA.xsd)

- Maintenance elements.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/ARML> (ARML.xsd)

- Augmented reality elements.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/SCORM> (SCORM.xsd)

- Elements related to the training activities.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/OpenSocial> (OpenSocial.xsd)

- Elements related to the social communication activities in the shop-floor.

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLschema/v1.0/Gaming> (Gaming.xsd)

- Elements related to the gamification activities in the shop-floor.

To simplify the instantiation, XSD schemas use the unqualified form of elements and attributes:

```
elementFormDefault="unqualified" attributeFormDefault="unqualified"
```

For the storage, CIDEM will still have to choose appropriate technology. NoSQL and XML databases are the probable choice, as it will make transformation from/to XML straightforward. However this still has to be decided during the upcoming project development phases.

CONCLUSION

This report presented the analysis of requirements to the SatisFactory Common Information Data Exchange Model (CIDEM). Existing information models from area of factories were analysed. CIDEM elements were described (using XSD schemas) and their usage was in the specification section. Technologically the proposed CIDEM is a set of XSD schemas defining several data elements needed for exchange of information between SatisFactory components. It was proposed that these components access CIDEM via CIDEM API.

The documentation of XSD schemas is provided in Annex I.

The CIDEM was designed to provide definition of SatisFactory shared vocabulary and meta-data. Proposed CIDEM contains the description of the information sources from particular modules to be able to use them within pilot execution. Therefore it can be the backbone for the system. Furthermore basic interfaces have been implemented for the communication of the CIDEM with the rest of the SatisFactory components.

In this state of the project it became clear that the current version of the CIDEM is not the final one. There are still ongoing discussions that are/will be reflected in CIDEM. Also the use of CIDEM after the first implementation will for sure bring some new requirements to be adopted in it. Furthermore, the implementation of the technical parts of the project will provide valuable information, which will be evaluated and included in the next iterations of the deliverable.

REFERENCES

- [1] SatisFactory Grant Agreement Annex I – “Description of Work” (DoW)
- [2] Common Information Model (computing)
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Common_Information_Model_%28computing%29
(11/06/2015)
- [3] SatisFactory Deliverable D2.1, D2.1 “SatisFactory System Architecture”, August 2015
- [4] Adapt4EE project, <http://www.adapt4ee.eu/>
- [5] INERTIA project, <http://www.inertia-project.eu/>

ANNEX I: SATISFACTORY CIDEM XSD FILES DOCUMENTATION

SCHEMA SATISFACTORY.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: **unqualified**
 elementFormDefault: **qualified**
 targetNamespace: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/>

Elements

CIDEM

Complex Types

SFInformationModel_Type
 SFSocialCommunication_Type
 SFGamification_Type

element CIDEM

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/
children	ShopFloorID, SFInformationModel, SFEvents, SFSocialCommunication, SFGamification
source	<pre> <xs:element name="CIDEM"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element name="ShopFloor" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element name="ShopFloorID" type="xs:string" /> <xs:element name="SFInformationModel" type="SFInformationModel_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element name="SFEvents" type="SFEvents_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element name="SFSocialCommunication" type="SFSocialCommunication_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element name="SFGamification" type="SFGamification_Type" minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </pre>

	<pre> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </pre>
--	--

complexType **SFInformationModel_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/
children	ShopFloor , EquipmentList , SensorList , AssetsList , ActorsList , ProceduresList , ARModelList
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="SFInformationModel_Type"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element name="ShopFloor" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" > <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element ref="gbxml:gbXML" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" /> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> <xs:element name="EquipmentList" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" > <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="B2MML:EquipmentInformationType" name="Equipment" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" /> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>

	<pre> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> <xs:element name="SensorList" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" > <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="SFcommon:tSensorInformation" name="Sensor" maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> <xs:element name="AssetsList" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" > <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetInformationType" name="Asset" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" /> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> <xs:element name="ActorsList" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" > <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="B2MML:PersonnelInformationType" name="Actor" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" /> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> <xs:element name="ProceduresList" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" > <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="B2MML:ProcessSegmentInformationType" name="Procedure" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" /> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> <xs:element name="ARModelList" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" > <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="ArmlType" name="ARModel" maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>
--	---

complexType **SFEvents_Type**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/</p>
<p>children</p>	<p>Measurement, Alert, Maintenance, ReAdaptation, ARevent, Training</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xs:complexType name="SFEvents_Type"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element name="EventList" maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="ID"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Type"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="TimeStamp"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Space"/> <xs:element name="Content"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="B2MML:OpSegmentDataType" name="Measurement" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="B2MML:WorkAlertInformationType" name="Alert" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element name="Maintenance" minOccurs="0"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="MIMOSA:sg_proposed_eventTYPE" name="Diagnosis" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="MIMOSA:sg_recommendationTYPE" name="Recommendations" minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>

	<pre> <xs:element type="B2MML:ProcessSegmentInformationType" name="ReAdaptation" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="DynamicFeatureCollectionType" name="ARevent" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="SCORM:TrainingType" name="Training" minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>
--	--

complexType **SFSocialCommunication_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/
children	Person, Group, Activity
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="SFSocialCommunication_Type"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element name="CommunicationList" maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="ID"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Type"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Timestamp"/> <xs:element name="Content"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="OPENSOCIAL:Person" name="Person" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="OPENSOCIAL:Group" name="Group" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="OPENSOCIAL:Activity" name="Activity" </pre>

	<pre> minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>
--	--

complexType **SFGamification_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/
children	Gaming-event
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="SFGamification_Type"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element name="GamificationList" maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0"> <xs:complexType> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="ID"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Type"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Timestamp"/> <xs:element ref="GAMIFICATION:Gaming-event"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </xs:element> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>

SCHEMA SATISFACTORY-COMMON.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: [unqualified](#)
 elementFormDefault: [qualified](#)
 targetNamespace: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common>

Elements

Complex Types

Simple Types

tMeasurementContentInformation
 tSensorInformation
 tPosition
 tValue

tSensorType
 tLengthUnitEnum
 tValueUnit

complexType **tMeasurementContentInformation**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common</p>
<p>children</p>	<p>tPosition</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre><xs:complexType name="tSensorInformation"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="ID"/> <xs:element type="SFcommon:tSensorType" name="Type"/> <xs:element type="SFcommon:tPosition" name="Position"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Space" minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **tSensorInformation**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common</p>
<p>children</p>	<p>tPosition</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xs:complexType name="tSensorInformation"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="ID"/> <xs:element type="SFcommon:tSensorType" name="Type"/> <xs:element type="SFcommon:tPosition" name="Position"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Space" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Interface" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Address" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="PacketLoss" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="PacketRate" minOccurs="0"/> <xs:element type="xs:string" name="Latency" minOccurs="0"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **tPosition**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="tPosition"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="xs:float" name="x"/> <xs:element type="xs:float" name="y"/> <xs:element type="xs:float" name="z"/> <xs:element type="SFcommon:tLengthUnitEnum" name="Unit"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **tValue**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="tValue"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element type="xs:float" name="Value"/> <xs:element type="SFcommon:tValueUnit" name="Unit"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType> </pre>

simpleType **tSensorType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common
type	string
source	<pre> <xs:simpleType name="tSensorType" final="restriction"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="DepthCamera"/> <xs:enumeration value="ThermalCamera"/> <xs:enumeration value="Accelerometer"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType> </pre>

	<pre> <xs:enumeration value="Gyroscope"/> <xs:enumeration value="CardioSensor"/> <xs:enumeration value="TempSensor"/> <xs:enumeration value="RFID"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType> </pre>
--	--

simpleType **tLengthUnitEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common
type	string
source	<pre> <xs:simpleType name="tLengthUnitEnum"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="Kilometres"/> <xs:enumeration value="Meters"/> <xs:enumeration value="Centimetres"/> <xs:enumeration value="Millimetres"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType> </pre>

simpleType **tValueUnit**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/common
type	string
source	<pre> <xs:simpleType name="tValueUnit"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="Celsius"/> <xs:enumeration value="Percentage"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType> </pre>

SCHEMA GBXML_v5.12.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: **unqualified**
 elementFormDefault: **qualified**
 targetNamespace: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/gbXML>

It is a common XSD schema, which has been used without any intervention. Thus, the description of its XSD schema is omitted.

SCHEMA B2MML.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: **unqualified**

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elementFormDefault:

qualified

targetNamespace:

<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML>

Elements

EquipmentInformation
PersonnelInformation
PhysicalAssetInformation
ProcessSegmentInformation

Complex Types

AnyGenericValueType
AssemblyRelationship1Type
AssemblyRelationshipType
AssemblyType1Type
AssemblyTypeType
DataType1Type
DataTypeType
Dependency1Type
DependencyType
DescriptionType
EquipmentAssetMappingType
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
EquipmentClassIDType
EquipmentElementLevel1Type
EquipmentElementLevelType
EquipmentIDType
ExpirationTimeType
HierarchyScopeType
LocationType
MaterialClassIDType
MaterialDefinitionIDType
MaterialUse1Type
MaterialUseType
OperationsType1Type
OperationsTypeType
ParameterType
PersonIDType
PersonNameType
PersonnelClassIDType
PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType
PhysicalAssetClassIDType
PhysicalAssetIDType
PriorityType
ProcessSegmentIDType
ProductProductionRuleIDType
ProductSegmentIDType
PropertyIDType
PublishedDateType
QualificationTestSpecificationIDType
QuantityStringType
QuantityValueType
RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponse1Type
RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponseType
ResultType

Simple Types

DurationType

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SegmentDependencyType
StartTimeType
TestDateTimeType
TestResultType
UnitOfMeasureType
ValueStringType
ValueType
VersionType
CodeType
DateTimeType
IdentifierType
NameType
NumericType
TextType
EquipmentInformationType
EquipmentType
EquipmentPropertyType
EquipmentClassType
EquipmentClassPropertyType
EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType
TestedEquipmentPropertyType
TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType
OpSegmentDataType
PersonnelInformationType
PersonType
PersonPropertyType
PersonnelClassType
PersonnelClassPropertyType
QualificationTestSpecificationType
TestedPersonPropertyType
TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType
PhysicalAssetInformationType
PhysicalAssetType
PhysicalAssetPropertyType
PhysicalAssetClassType
PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType
TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType
TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType
ProcessSegmentInformationType
ProcessSegmentType
PersonnelSegmentSpecificationType
PersonnelSegmentSpecificationPropertyType
EquipmentSegmentSpecificationType
EquipmentSegmentSpecificationPropertyType
PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationType
PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationPropertyType
MaterialSegmentSpecificationType

MaterialSegmentSpecificationPropertyType
 WorkAlertInformationType
 WorkAlertDefinitionType
 WorkAlertType
 WorkAlertPropertyType

element **EquipmentInformation**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<xsd:element name="EquipmentInformation" type="B2MML:EquipmentInformationType"/>

element **PersonnelInformation**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<xsd:element name="PersonnelInformation" type="B2MML:PersonnelInformationType"/>

element **PhysicalAssetInformation**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetInformation" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetInformationType"/>

element **ProcessSegmentInformation**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<xsd:element name="ProcessSegmentInformation" type="B2MML:ProcessSegmentInformationType"/>

complexType **AnyGenericType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<xsd:complexType name="AnyGenericType"> <xsd:simpleContent>

	<pre> <xsd:extension base="xsd:string"> <xsd:attribute name="currencyID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="currencyCodeListVersionID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="encodingCode" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="format" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="characterSetCode" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listAgencyID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listAgencyName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listVersionID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="languageID" type="xsd:language" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="languageLocaleID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listSchemaURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="mimeCode" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="name" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemaID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemaName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemaAgencyID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemaAgencyName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemaVersionID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemaDataURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemaURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="unitCode" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="unitCodeListID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="unitCodeListAgencyID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="unitCodeListAgencyName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="unitCodeListVersionID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="filename" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="uri" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> </pre>
--	---

	<pre> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </xs:complexType> </pre>
--	---

complexType **AssemblyRelationship1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="AssemblyRelationship1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="B2MML:Permanent"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Transient"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **AssemblyRelationshipType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="AssemblyRelationshipType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:AssemblyRelationship1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **AssemblyType1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="AssemblyType1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="Physical"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Logical"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **AssemblyTypeType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="AssemblyTypeType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:AssemblyType1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **DataType1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="DataType1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="Amount"/> <xsd:enumeration value="BinaryObject"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Code"/> <xsd:enumeration value="DateTime"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Identifier"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Indicator"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Measure"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Numeric"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Quantity"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Text"/> <xsd:enumeration value="string"/> <xsd:enumeration value="byte"/> <xsd:enumeration value="unsignedByte"/> <xsd:enumeration value="binary"/> <xsd:enumeration value="integer"/> <xsd:enumeration value="positiveInteger"/> <xsd:enumeration value="negativeInteger"/> <xsd:enumeration value="nonNegativeInteger"/> <xsd:enumeration value="nonPositiveInteger"/> <xsd:enumeration value="int"/> <xsd:enumeration value="unsignedInt"/> <xsd:enumeration value="long"/> <xsd:enumeration value="unsignedLong"/> <xsd:enumeration value="short"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

	<pre> <xsd:enumeration value="unsignedShort"/> <xsd:enumeration value="decimal"/> <xsd:enumeration value="float"/> <xsd:enumeration value="double"/> <xsd:enumeration value="boolean"/> <xsd:enumeration value="time"/> <xsd:enumeration value="timeInstant"/> <xsd:enumeration value="timePeriod"/> <xsd:enumeration value="duration"/> <xsd:enumeration value="date"/> <xsd:enumeration value="dateTime"/> <xsd:enumeration value="month"/> <xsd:enumeration value="year"/> <xsd:enumeration value="century"/> <xsd:enumeration value="recurringDay"/> <xsd:enumeration value="recurringDate"/> <xsd:enumeration value="recurringDuration"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Name"/> <xsd:enumeration value="QName"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NCName"/> <xsd:enumeration value="uriReference"/> <xsd:enumeration value="language"/> <xsd:enumeration value="ID"/> <xsd:enumeration value="IDREF"/> <xsd:enumeration value="IDREFS"/> <xsd:enumeration value="ENTITY"/> <xsd:enumeration value="ENTITIES"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NOTATION"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NMTOKEN"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NMTOKENS"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Enumeration"/> <xsd:enumeration value="SVG"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
--	--

complexType DataTypeType

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="DataTypeType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:DataType1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

	<pre></xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>
--	--

complexType **Dependency1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="Dependency1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="NotFollow"/> <xsd:enumeration value="PossibleParallel"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NotInParallel"/> <xsd:enumeration value="AtStart"/> <xsd:enumeration value="AfterStart"/> <xsd:enumeration value="AfterEnd"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NoLaterAfterStart"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NoEarlierAfterStart"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NoLaterAfterEnd"/> <xsd:enumeration value="NoEarlierAfterEnd"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **DependencyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="DependencyType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:Dependency1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **DescriptionType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="DescriptionType"> <xsd:simpleContent></pre>

	<pre><xsd:restriction base="B2MML:TextType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>
--	---

complexType **EquipmentAssetMappingType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="EquipmentAssetMappingType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="EquipmentID" type="B2MML:EquipmentIDType"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetIDType"/> <xsd:element name="StartTime" type="B2MML:DateTimeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EndTime" type="B2MML:DateTimeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentAssetMapping" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **EquipmentClassIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML

source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="EquipmentClassIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>
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complexType **EquipmentElementLevel1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="EquipmentElementLevel1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="Enterprise"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Site"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Area"/> <xsd:enumeration value="ProcessCell"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Unit"/> <xsd:enumeration value="ProductionLine"/> <xsd:enumeration value="WorkCell"/> <xsd:enumeration value="ProductionUnit"/> <xsd:enumeration value="StorageZone"/> <xsd:enumeration value="StorageUnit"/> <xsd:enumeration value="WorkCenter"/> <xsd:enumeration value="WorkUnit"/> <xsd:enumeration value="EquipmentModule"/> <xsd:enumeration value="ControlModule"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **EquipmentElementLevelType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="EquipmentElementLevelType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:EquipmentElementLevel1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **EquipmentIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="EquipmentIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **ExpirationTimeType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="ExpirationTimeType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:DateTimeType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **HierarchyScopeType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="HierarchyScopeType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="EquipmentID" type="B2MML:EquipmentIDType"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentElementLevel" type="B2MML:EquipmentElementLevelType"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:HierarchyScope" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **LocationType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="LocationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="EquipmentID" type="B2MML:EquipmentIDType"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentElementLevel" type="B2MML:EquipmentElementLevelType"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:Location" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **MaterialClassIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="MaterialClassIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **MaterialDefinitionIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="MaterialDefinitionIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **MaterialUse1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="MaterialUse1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="Consumed"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Produced"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Consumable"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Replaced Assetn"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Replacement Asset"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Sample"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Returned Sample"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Carrier"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Returned Carrier"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **MaterialUseType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="MaterialUseType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:MaterialUse1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **OperationsType1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="OperationsType1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="Production"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Maintenance"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

	<pre> <xsd:enumeration value="Quality"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Inventory"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Mixed"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
--	---

complexType **OperationsType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="OperationsType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:OperationsType1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **ParameterType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="ParameterType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Parameter" type="B2MML:ParameterType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:Parameter" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </pre>

	</xsd:complexType>
--	--------------------

complexType **PersonIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PersonIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PersonNameType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PersonNameType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PersonnelClassIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PersonnelClassIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PhysicalAssetClassIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetClassIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PhysicalAssetIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PriorityType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PriorityType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:NumericType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **ProcessSegmentIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="ProcessSegmentIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **ProductProductionRuleIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="ProductProductionRuleIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **ProductSegmentIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="ProductSegmentIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PropertyIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PropertyIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **PublishedDateType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="PublishedDateType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:DateTimeType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **QualificationTestSpecificationIDType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="QualificationTestSpecificationIDType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **QuantityStringType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="QuantityStringType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:AnyGenericType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **QuantityValueType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="QuantityValueType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="QuantityString" type="B2MML:QuantityStringType" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="DataType" type="B2MML:DataTypeType" nillable="true" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="UnitOfMeasure" type="B2MML:UnitOfMeasureType" nillable="true" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Key" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

	<pre>maxOccurs="1"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:Quantity" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>
--	--

complexType **RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponse1Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponse1Type"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"> <xsd:enumeration value="Required"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Optional"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponseType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponseType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="B2MML:RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponse1Type"> <xsd:attribute name="OtherValue" type="xsd:string"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType ResultType

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="ResultType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ValueString" type="B2MML:ValueStringType" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="DataType" type="B2MML:DataTypeType" nillable="true" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="UnitOfMeasure" type="B2MML:UnitOfMeasureType" nillable="true" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Key" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:Result" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType SegmentDependencyType

<p>diagram</p>	
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namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="SegmentDependencyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Dependency" type="B2MML:DependencyType"/> <xsd:element name="TimingFactor" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:choice minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"> <xsd:element name="ProductSegmentID" type="B2MML:ProductSegmentIDType"/> <xsd:element name="ProcessSegmentID" type="B2MML:ProcessSegmentIDType"/> <xsd:element name="SegmentID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:choice> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:SegmentDependency" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **StartTimeType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="StartTimeType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:DateTimeType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TestDateTimeType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TestDateTimeType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:DateTimeType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TestResultType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TestResultType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="TestDateTime" type="B2MML:TestDateTimeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Result" type="B2MML:ResultType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="ExpirationTime" type="B2MML:ExpirationTimeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:TestResult" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **UnitOfMeasureType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="UnitOfMeasureType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:CodeType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **ValueStringType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="ValueStringType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:AnyGenericType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **ValueType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="ValueType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ValueString" type="B2MML:ValueStringType" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="DataType" type="B2MML:DataTypeType" nillable="true" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="UnitOfMeasure" type="B2MML:UnitOfMeasureType" nillable="true" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Key" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:Value" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **VersionType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML

source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="VersionType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:restriction base="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>
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complexType **CodeType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="CodeType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="xsd:normalizedString"> <xsd:attribute name="listID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listAgencyID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listAgencyName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listVersionID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="name" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="languageID" type="xsd:language" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="listSchemeURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **DateTimeType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="DateTimeType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="xsd:dateTime"> <xsd:attribute name="format" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **IdentifierType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML

source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="IdentifierType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="xsd:normalizedString"> <xsd:attribute name="schemeID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemeName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemeAgencyID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemeAgencyName" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemeVersionID" type="xsd:normalizedString" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemeDataURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> <xsd:attribute name="schemeURI" type="xsd:anyURI" use="optional"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **NameType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="NameType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="xsd:string"> <xsd:attribute name="languageID" type="xsd:language" use="optional"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **NumericType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="NumericType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="xsd:decimal"> <xsd:attribute name="format" type="xsd:string" use="optional"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TextType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TextType"> <xsd:simpleContent> <xsd:extension base="xsd:string"> <xsd:attribute name="languageID" type="xsd:language" use="optional"/> </xsd:extension> </xsd:simpleContent> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **EquipmentInformationType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentInformationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PublishedDate" type="B2MML:PublishedDateType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Equipment" type="B2MML:EquipmentType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </pre>

	<pre> <xsd:element name="EquipmentClass" type="B2MML:EquipmentClassType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification" type="B2MML:EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentInformation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **EquipmentType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" </pre>

	<pre> minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentLevel" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentAssetMapping" type="B2MML:EquipmentAssetMappingType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentProperty" type="B2MML:EquipmentPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Equipment" type="B2MML:EquipmentType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentClassID" type="B2MML:EquipmentClassIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:Equipment" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType EquipmentPropertyType

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentProperty" type="B2MML:EquipmentPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID" </pre>

	<pre> type="B2MML:EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="TestResult" type="B2MML:TestResultType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **EquipmentClassType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentClassType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentLevel" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentClassProperty" type="B2MML:EquipmentClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentID" type="B2MML:EquipmentIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </pre>

	<pre> <xsd:element name="EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentClass" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **EquipmentClassPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentClassPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentClassProperty" type="B2MML:EquipmentClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentClassProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecificationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Name" type="B2MML:NameType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Version" type="B2MML:VersionType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TestedEquipmentProperty" type="B2MML:TestedEquipmentPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="TestedEquipmentClassProperty" type="B2MML:TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentCapabilityTestSpecification" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TestedEquipmentPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TestedEquipmentPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="EquipmentID" type="B2MML:EquipmentIDType"/> <xsd:element name="PropertyID" type="B2MML:PropertyIDType"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:TestedEquipmentProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TestedEquipmentClassPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="EquipmentClassID" type="B2MML:EquipmentClassIDType"/> <xsd:element name="PropertyID" type="B2MML:PropertyIDType"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:TestedEquipmentClassProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **OpSegmentDataType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="OpSegmentDataType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="SegmentData" type="B2MML:OpSegmentDataType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponse" type="B2MML:RequiredByRequestedSegmentResponseType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:OpSegmentData" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PersonnelInformationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PersonnelInformationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PublishedDate" type="B2MML:PublishedDateType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Person" type="B2MML:PersonType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PersonnelClass" type="B2MML:PersonnelClassType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="QualificationTestSpecification" type="B2MML:QualificationTestSpecificationType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PersonnelInformation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PersonType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PersonType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PersonName" type="B2MML:PersonNameType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PersonProperty" type="B2MML:PersonPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PersonnelClassID" type="B2MML:PersonnelClassIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="QualificationTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:QualificationTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:Person" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PersonPropertyType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PersonPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PersonProperty" type="B2MML:PersonPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="QualificationTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:QualificationTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="TestResult" type="B2MML:TestResultType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PersonProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PersonnelClassType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PersonnelClassType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PersonnelClassProperty" type="B2MML:PersonnelClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PersonID" type="B2MML:PersonIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="QualificationTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:QualificationTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PersonnelClass" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PersonnelClassPropertyType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PersonnelClassPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PersonnelClassProperty" type="B2MML:PersonnelClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="QualificationTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:QualificationTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PersonnelClassProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **QualificationTestSpecificationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="QualificationTestSpecificationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Version" type="B2MML:VersionType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TestedPersonProperty" type="B2MML:TestedPersonPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="TestedPersonnelClassProperty" type="B2MML:TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:QualificationTestSpecification" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TestedPersonPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TestedPersonPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="PersonID" type="B2MML:PersonIDType"/> <xsd:element name="PropertyID" type="B2MML:PropertyIDType"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:TestedPersonProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TestedPersonnelClassPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="PersonnelClassID" type="B2MML:PersonnelClassIDType"/> <xsd:element name="PropertyID" type="B2MML:PropertyIDType"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:TestedPersonnelClassProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PhysicalAssetInformationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetInformationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PublishedDate" type="B2MML:PublishedDateType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAsset" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetClass" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClassType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAssetInformation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PhysicalAssetType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalLocation" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="FixedAssetID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> </pre>

	<pre> <xsd:element name="VendorID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentLevel" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentAssetMapping" type="B2MML:EquipmentAssetMappingType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetProperty" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAsset" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetClassID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClassIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAsset" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType PhysicalAssetPropertyType

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetProperty" </pre>

<pre> type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetPropertyType" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="TestResult" type="B2MML:TestResultType" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAssetProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>	<pre> minOccurs="0" minOccurs="0" minOccurs="0" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1" </pre>
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complexType **PhysicalAssetClassType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetClassType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Manufacturer" type="B2MML:NameType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetClassProperty" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetIDType" </pre>

	<pre> minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClass" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
--	---

complexType **PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetClassProperty" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationIDType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClassProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecificationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Name" type="B2MML:NameType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Version" type="B2MML:VersionType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TestedPhysicalAssetProperty" type="B2MML:TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty" type="B2MML:TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAssetCapabilityTestSpecification" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType**

<p>diagram</p>	
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namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="TestedPhysicalAssetPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetIDType"/> <xsd:element name="PropertyID" type="B2MML:PropertyIDType"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:TestedPhysicalAssetProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="TestedPhysicalAssetClassPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetClassID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClassIDType"/> <xsd:element name="PropertyID" type="B2MML:PropertyIDType"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:TestedPhysicalAssetClassProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **ProcessSegmentInformationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="ProcessSegmentInformationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PublishedDate" type="B2MML:PublishedDateType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="ProcessSegment" type="B2MML:ProcessSegmentType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:ProcessSegmentInformation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **ProcessSegmentType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre><xsd:complexType name="ProcessSegmentType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="OperationsType" type="B2MML:OperationsTypeType" minOccurs="0"/></pre>

	<pre> <xsd:element name="Location" type="B2MML:LocationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PublishedDate" type="B2MML:PublishedDateType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Duration" type="B2MML:DurationType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PersonnelSegmentSpecification" type="B2MML:PersonnelSegmentSpecificationType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentSegmentSpecification" type="B2MML:EquipmentSegmentSpecificationType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecification" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="MaterialSegmentSpecification" type="B2MML:MaterialSegmentSpecificationType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Parameter" type="B2MML:ParameterType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="SegmentDependency" type="B2MML:SegmentDependencyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="ProcessSegment" type="B2MML:ProcessSegmentType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:ProcessSegment" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **PersonnelSegmentSpecificationType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML

source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PersonnelSegmentSpecificationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="PersonnelClassID" type="B2MML:PersonnelClassIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PersonID" type="B2MML:PersonIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PersonnelUse" type="B2MML:CodeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PersonnelSegmentSpecificationProperty" type="B2MML:PersonnelSegmentSpecificationPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PersonnelSegmentSpecification" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **PersonnelSegmentSpecificationPropertyType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PersonnelSegmentSpecificationPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PersonnelSegmentSpecificationProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **EquipmentSegmentSpecificationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentSegmentSpecificationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="EquipmentClassID" type="B2MML:EquipmentClassIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentID" type="B2MML:EquipmentIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentUse" type="B2MML:CodeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="EquipmentSegmentSpecificationProperty" type="B2MML:EquipmentSegmentSpecificationPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentSegmentSpecification" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **EquipmentSegmentSpecificationPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="EquipmentSegmentSpecificationPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:EquipmentSegmentSpecificationProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML

source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetClassID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetClassIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetID" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetUse" type="B2MML:CodeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationProperty" type="B2MML:PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecification" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationPropertyType

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:PhysicalAssetSegmentSpecificationProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </pre>

	</xsd:complexType>
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complexType **MaterialSegmentSpecificationType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
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source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="MaterialSegmentSpecificationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="MaterialClassID" type="B2MML:MaterialClassIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="MaterialDefinitionID" type="B2MML:MaterialDefinitionIDType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="AssemblyType" type="B2MML:AssemblyTypeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="AssemblyRelationship" type="B2MML:AssemblyRelationshipType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="AssemblySpecificationID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="MaterialUse" type="B2MML:MaterialUseType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" </pre>
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	<pre> maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="MaterialSegmentSpecificationProperty" type="B2MML:MaterialSegmentSpecificationPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:MaterialSegmentSpecification" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **MaterialSegmentSpecificationPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="MaterialSegmentSpecificationPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Quantity" type="B2MML:QuantityValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:MaterialSegmentSpecificationProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **WorkAlertInformationType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre><xsd:complexType name="WorkAlertInformationType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="PublishedDate" type="B2MML:PublishedDateType" minOccurs="0" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="WorkAlertDefinition" type="B2MML:WorkAlertDefinitionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" nillable="true"/> <xsd:element name="WorkAlert" type="B2MML:WorkAlertType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" nillable="true"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:WorkAlertInformation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **WorkAlertDefinitionType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="WorkAlertDefinitionType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Priority" type="B2MML:PriorityType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Category" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Property" type="B2MML:WorkAlertPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:WorkAlertDefinition" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **WorkAlertType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="WorkAlertType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="MessageText" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="HierarchyScope" type="B2MML:HierarchyScopeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TimeStamp" type="B2MML:StartTimeType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Priority" type="B2MML:PriorityType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Category" type="B2MML:IdentifierType" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Property" type="B2MML:WorkAlertPropertyType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:WorkAlert" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **WorkAlertPropertyType**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="WorkAlertPropertyType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="B2MML:IdentifierType"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="B2MML:DescriptionType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:element name="Value" type="B2MML:ValueType" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <xsd:group ref="B2MML:WorkAlertProperty" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="1"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

simpleType **DurationType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/B2MML
type	duration
source	<pre> <xsd:simpleType name="DurationType"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:duration"/> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>

SCHEMA MIMOSA.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: [unqualified](#)
elementFormDefault: [qualified](#)
targetNamespace: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/MIMOSA>

Elements

Complex Types

[linfo](#)
[sg_proposed_eventTYPE](#)
[sg_recommendationTYPE](#)

Simple Types

[varchar254](#)
[site_codeSimpleType](#)
[dateTimeWithoutTimezone](#)

complexType Icinfo

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/MIMOSA
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="Icinfo"> <xsd:sequence minOccurs="1" maxOccurs="unbounded"> <xsd:element name="attr_name" type="xsd:string"> </xsd:element> <xsd:element name="value" type="xsd:string"> </xsd:element> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType sg_proposed_eventTYPE

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/MIMOSA
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="sg_proposed_eventTYPE"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Icinfo" type="Icinfo" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> <xsd:attribute name="sg_prop_db_site" use="required" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="sg_prop_db_id" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="sg_prop_event_id" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="segment_site" use="required" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="segment_id" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="ev_db_site" use="required" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="ev_db_id" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="event_type_code" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="severity_lev_db_site" use="required" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="severity_lev_db_id" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </pre>

<pre> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="severity_lev_type_code" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="gmt_proposed" use="optional" type="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="pr_loc_hr_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:short"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="pr_loc_min_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="by_org_asite" use="optional" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="by_agent_id" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="likelihood_prob" use="optional" type="xsd:double"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="est_gmt_start" use="optional" type="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="st_loc_hr_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:short"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="st_loc_min_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="est_gmt_occur_end" use="optional" type="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="end_loc_hr_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:short"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="end_loc_min_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="ch_patt_db_site" use="optional" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="ch_patt_db_id" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="ch_patt_type_code" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="user_tag_ident" use="optional" type="varchar254"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="name" use="optional" type="varchar254"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="gmt_audited" use="optional" type="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> </xsd:attribute> </pre>
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	<pre> <xsd:attribute name="aud_loc_hr_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:short"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="aud_loc_min_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="aud_quality_code" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="aud_by_org_asite" use="optional" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="aud_by_agent_id" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="gmt_last_updated" use="optional" type="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="last_upd_db_site" use="optional" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="last_upd_db_id" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="rstat_type_code" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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complexType **sg_recommendationTYPE**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/MIMOSA
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="sg_recommendationTYPE"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="linfo" type="linfo" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> <xsd:attribute name="segment_site" use="required" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="segment_id" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="gmt_recommendation" use="required" type="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="by_agent_site" use="required" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="by_agent_id" use="required" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> </pre>

	<pre> <xsd:attribute name="loc_hr_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:short"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="loc_min_delta" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="priority_lev_db_site" use="optional" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="priority_lev_db_id" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="priority_lev_type_code" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="user_tag_ident" use="optional" type="varchar254"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="name" use="optional" type="varchar254"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="gmt_last_updated" use="optional" type="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="last_upd_db_site" use="optional" type="site_codeSimpleType"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="last_upd_db_id" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedInt"> </xsd:attribute> <xsd:attribute name="rstat_type_code" use="optional" type="xsd:unsignedShort"> </xsd:attribute> </xsd:complexType> </pre>
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simpleType **varchar254**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/MIMOSA
type	string
source	<pre> <xsd:simpleType name="varchar254"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:maxLength value="254"> </xsd:maxLength> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>

simpleType **site_codeSimpleType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/MIMOSA
type	hexBinary
source	<pre> <xsd:simpleType name="site_codeSimpleType"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:hexBinary"> <xsd:length value="8"> </xsd:length> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>

	</xsd:simpleType>
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simpleType **dateTimeWithoutTimezone**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/MIMOSA
type	dateTime
source	<pre><xsd:simpleType name="dateTimeWithoutTimezone"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:dateTime"> <xsd:pattern value="[0-9]{4}-[0-9]{2}-[0-9]{2}T[0-9]{2}:[0-9]{2}:[0-9]{2}\.?[0-9]{0,9}"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType></pre>

SCHEMA ARML.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: **unqualified**
 elementFormDefault: **qualified**
 targetNamespace: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/ARML>

It is a common XSD schema, which has been used without any intervention. Thus, the description of its XSD schema is omitted.

SCHEMA SCORM.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: **unqualified**
 elementFormDefault: **qualified**
 targetNamespace: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM>

Elements

Complex Types

TrainingType
 CommentList_Type
 Comment_Type
 InteractionList_Type
 Interaction_Type
 LearnerPreferencesList_Type
 LearnerPreferences_Type
 ObjectivesList_Type
 Objective_Type
 ScoreList_Type
 Score_Type
 result_Type

Simple Types

completionStatusEnum
 creditEnum
 interactionTypeEnum
 resultTypeEnum
 audioCaptioningEnum
 modeEnum
 successStatusEnum
 timeLimitActionEnum

complexType **TrainingType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="TrainingType"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="LearnerID" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Interactions" type="InteractionList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="LearnerPreferences" type="LearnerPreferencesList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="MaxTimeAllowed" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Mode" type="modeEnum" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Objectives" type="ObjectivesList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="ProgressMeasure" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="ScaledPassingScore" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Scores" type="ScoreList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="SessionTime" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="SuccessStatus" type="successStatusEnum" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TimeLimitAction" type="timeLimitActionEnum" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TotalTime" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="LaunchData" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="CommentsFromLearner" type="CommentList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="CommentsFromLMS" type="CommentList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="CompletionStatus" type="completionStatusEnum" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="CompletionThreshold" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Credit" type="creditEnum" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **CommentList_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="CommentList_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Comment" type="Comment_Type" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </xsd:sequence> </pre>

	</xsd:complexType>
--	--------------------

complexType **Comment_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="Comment_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Comment" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Location" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TimeStamp" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **InteractionList_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre><xsd:complexType name="InteractionList_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Interaction" type="Interaction_Type" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType></pre>

complexType **Interaction_Type**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="Interaction_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Type" type="interactionTypeEnum" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Objectives" type="ObjectivesList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="TimeStamp" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="CorrectResponses" type="xsd:integer" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Weighting" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="LearnerResponse" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Result" type="result_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Latency" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **LearnerPreferencesList_Type**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="LearnerPreferencesList_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="LearnerPreferences" type="LearnerPreferences_Type" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </xsd:sequence> </pre>

	</xsd:complexType>
--	--------------------

complexType LearnerPreferences_Type

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="LearnerPreferences_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Language" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="DeliverySpeed" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="AudioLevel" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="AudioCaptioning" type="audioCaptioningEnum" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType ObjectivesList_Type

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="ObjectivesList_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Objective" type="Objective_Type" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Objective_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="Objective_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="ID" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Scores" type="ScoreList_Type" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="SuccessStatus" type="successStatusEnum" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="CompletionStatus" type="completionStatusEnum" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="ProgressMeasure" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Description" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **ScoreList_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="ScoreList_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Score" type="Score_Type" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Score_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="Score_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Scaled" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Raw" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Min" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Max" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

complexType **result_Type**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
source	<pre> <xsd:complexType name="result_Type"> <xsd:sequence> <xsd:element name="Numeric" type="xsd:float" minOccurs="0"/> <xsd:element name="Characterization" type="resultTypeEnum" minOccurs="0"/> </xsd:sequence> </xsd:complexType> </pre>

simpleType **completionStatusEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	string
source	<pre> <xsd:simpleType name="completionStatusEnum" final="restriction"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:enumeration value="Completed"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Incomplete"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Not attended"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Unknown"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>

simpleType **creditEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	string
source	<pre><xsd:simpleType name="creditEnum" final="restriction"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:enumeration value="Credit"/> <xsd:enumeration value="No-Credit"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **interactionTypeEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	string
source	<pre><xsd:simpleType name="interactionTypeEnum" final="restriction"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:enumeration value="true-false"/> <xsd:enumeration value="choice"/> <xsd:enumeration value="fill-in"/> <xsd:enumeration value="long-fill-in"/> <xsd:enumeration value="matching"/> <xsd:enumeration value="performance"/> <xsd:enumeration value="sequencing"/> <xsd:enumeration value="likert"/> <xsd:enumeration value="numeric"/> <xsd:enumeration value="other"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **resultTypeEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	string
source	<pre><xsd:simpleType name="resultTypeEnum" final="restriction"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:enumeration value="Correct"/> <xsd:enumeration value="choice"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Incorrect"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Unanticipated"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Neutral"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **audioCaptioningEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	integer
source	<pre><xsd:simpleType name="audioCaptioningEnum" final="restriction"></pre>

	<pre> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:integer"> <xsd:enumeration value="-1"/> <xsd:enumeration value="0"/> <xsd:enumeration value="1"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>
--	--

simpleType **modeEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	string
source	<pre> <xsd:simpleType name="modeEnum" final="restriction"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:enumeration value="Browse"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Normal"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Review"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>

simpleType **successStatusEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	string
source	<pre> <xsd:simpleType name="successStatusEnum" final="restriction"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:enumeration value="Passed"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Failed"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Unknown"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>

simpleType **timeLimitActionEnum**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/SCORM
type	string
source	<pre> <xsd:simpleType name="timeLimitActionEnum" final="restriction"> <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string"> <xsd:enumeration value="Exit"/> <xsd:enumeration value="Continue"/> </xsd:restriction> </xsd:simpleType> </pre>

SCHEMA OPENSOCIAL.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault: **unqualified**
 elementFormDefault: **qualified**

targetNamespace: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial>

Elements

Complex Types

Activity
ActivityTemplateParams
Person
Group
AppdataEntry
Appdata
BodyType
Address
Account
Organization
Name
Url
MediaItem
Drinker
Presence
Smoker
LookingFor
NetworkPresence
PluralPersonField

Simple Types

DrinkerType
PresenceType
LookingForType
SmokerType
NetworkPresenceType
MediaItemtype

complexType **Activity**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial</p>
<p>source</p>	<p><xs:complexType name="Activity"></p>

	<pre> <xs:choice minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="appld" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="body" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="bodyId" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="externalId" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="id" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="medialtems" type="tns:MediaItem"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="postedTime" type="xs:long"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="priority" type="xs:double"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="streamFaviconUrl" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="streamSourceUrl" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="streamTitle" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="streamUrl" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="templateParams" type="tns:ActivityTemplateParams"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="title" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="titleId" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="updated" type="xs:dateTime"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="url" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="userId" type="xs:string"/> </xs:choice> </xs:complexType> </pre>
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complexType ActivityTemplateParams

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="ActivityTemplateParams"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="PersonKey" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="PersonKey.DisplayName" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="PersonKey.Id" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="PersonKey.ProfileUrl" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="person" type="tns:Person"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType> </pre>

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="Person"> <xs:choice minOccurs="1" maxOccurs="unbounded"> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="aboutMe" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="accounts" type="tns:Account"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="activities" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="addresses" type="tns:Address"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="age" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="anniversary" type="xs:dateTime"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="appData" type="tns:Appdata"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="birthday" type="xs:dateTime"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="bodyType" type="tns:BodyType"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="books" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="cars" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="children" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="connected" type="tns:Presence"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="currentLocation" type="tns:Address"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="displayName" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="drinker" type="tns:Drinker"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="emails" type="tns:PluralPersonField"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="ethnicity" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="fashion" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="food" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="gender" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="happiestWhen" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="hasApp" type="xs:boolean"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="heroes" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="humor" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="id" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="ims" type="tns:PluralPersonField"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="interests" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="jobInterests" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="languagesSpoken" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="livingArrangement" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="lookingFor" type="tns:LookingFor"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="movies" type="xs:string"/> </pre>

SATISFACTORY

	<pre><xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="music" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="name" type="tns:Name"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="networkPresence" type="tns:NetworkPresence"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="nickname" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="organizations" type="tns:Organization"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="pets" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="phoneNumbers" type="tns:PluralPersonField"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="photos" type="tns:PluralPersonField"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="politicalViews" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="preferredUsername" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="profileSong" type="tns:Url"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="profileUrl" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="profileVideo" type="tns:Url"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="published" type="xs:dateTime"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="quotes" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="relationships" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="relationshipStatus" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="religion" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="romance" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="scaredOf" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="sexualOrientation" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="smoker" type="tns:Smoker"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="sports" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="status" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="tags" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="thumbnailUrl" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="turnOffs" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="turnOns" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="tvShows" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="updated" type="xs:dateTime"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="urls" type="tns:Url"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="utcOffset" type="xs:int"/> </xs:choice> </xs:complexType></pre>
--	--

complexType **Group**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="Group"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="id" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="title" type="xs:string"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **AppdataEntry**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="AppdataEntry" mixed="true"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="1" name="key" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="1" name="value" type="xs:anyType"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **Appdata**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="Appdata"> <xs:sequence> <xs:element minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" name="entry" type="tns:AppdataEntry"/> </xs:sequence> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **BodyType**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xs:complexType name="BodyType"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="build" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="eyeColor" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="hairColor" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="height" type="xs:double"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="weight" type="xs:double"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Address**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xs:complexType name="Address"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="country" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="extendedAddress" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="latitude" type="xs:double"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="locality" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="longitude" type="xs:double"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="poBox" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="postalCode" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="primary" type="xs:boolean"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="region" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="streetAddress" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="type" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="formatted" type="xs:string"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Account**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="Account"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="domain" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="primary" type="xs:boolean"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="userid" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="username" type="xs:string"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Organization**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <xs:complexType name="Organization"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="address" type="tns:Address"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="department" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="description" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="endDate" type="xs:dateTime"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="name" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="startDate" type="xs:dateTime"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="type" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="title" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="field" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="subField" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="webpage" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="salary" type="xs:string"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Name**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="Name"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="additionalName" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="familyName" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="givenName" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="honorificPrefix" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="honorificSuffix" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="formatted" type="xs:string"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Url**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre> <xs:complexType name="Url"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="value" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="linkText" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="type" type="xs:string"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType> </pre>

complexType **Medialtem**

diagram	<p>The diagram shows a complex type named 'Medialtem' with an 'all' cardinality. It contains three child elements: 'mimeType', 'type', and 'url'.</p>
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="Medialtem"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="mimeType" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="type" type="tns:MedialtemType"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="url" type="xs:string"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **Drinker**

diagram	<p>The diagram shows a complex type named 'Drinker' with an 'all' cardinality. It contains two child elements: 'displayValue' and 'value'.</p>
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="Drinker"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="displayValue" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="value" type="tns:DrinkerType"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **Presence**

diagram	<p>The diagram shows a complex type named 'Presence' with an 'all' cardinality. It contains two child elements: 'displayValue' and 'value'.</p>
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="Presence"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="displayValue" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="value" type="tns:PresenceType"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **Smoker**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="Smoker"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="displayValue" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="value" type="tns:SmokerType"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **LookingFor**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="LookingFor"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="displayValue" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="value" type="tns:LookingForType"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **NetworkPresence**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="NetworkPresence"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="displayValue" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="value" type="tns:NetworkPresenceType"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

complexType **PluralPersonField**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
source	<pre><xs:complexType name="PluralPersonField"> <xs:all> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="value" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="type" type="xs:string"/> <xs:element minOccurs="0" name="primary" type="xs:boolean"/> </xs:all> </xs:complexType></pre>

simpleType **DrinkerType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
type	string
source	<pre><xs:simpleType name="DrinkerType"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="HEAVILY"/> <xs:enumeration value="NO"/> <xs:enumeration value="OCCASIONALLY"/> <xs:enumeration value="QUIT"/> <xs:enumeration value="QUITTING"/> <xs:enumeration value="REGULARLY"/> <xs:enumeration value="SOCIALLY"/> <xs:enumeration value="YES"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **PresenceType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
type	string
source	<pre><xs:simpleType name="PresenceType"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="AWAY"/> <xs:enumeration value="CHAT"/> <xs:enumeration value="DND"/> <xs:enumeration value="OFFLINE"/> <xs:enumeration value="ONLINE"/> <xs:enumeration value="XA"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **LookingForType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
type	string
source	<pre><xs:simpleType name="LookingForType"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="ACTIVITY_PARTNERS"/> <xs:enumeration value="DATING"/> <xs:enumeration value="FRIENDS"/> <xs:enumeration value="NETWORKING"/> <xs:enumeration value="RANDOM"/> <xs:enumeration value="RELATIONSHIP"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **SmokerType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
type	string
source	<pre><xs:simpleType name="SmokerType"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="HEAVILY"/> <xs:enumeration value="NO"/> <xs:enumeration value="OCCASIONALLY"/> <xs:enumeration value="QUIT"/> <xs:enumeration value="QUITTING"/> <xs:enumeration value="REGULARLY"/> <xs:enumeration value="SOCIALLY"/> <xs:enumeration value="YES"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **NetworkPresenceType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
type	string
source	<pre><xs:simpleType name="NetworkPresenceType"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="AWAY"/> <xs:enumeration value="CHAT"/> <xs:enumeration value="DND"/> <xs:enumeration value="OFFLINE"/> <xs:enumeration value="ONLINE"/> <xs:enumeration value="XA"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType></pre>

simpleType **MedialtemType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/OpenSocial
type	string
source	<pre><xs:simpleType name="MedialtemType"> <xs:restriction base="xs:string"> <xs:enumeration value="AUDIO"/> <xs:enumeration value="IMAGE"/> <xs:enumeration value="VIDEO"/> </xs:restriction> </xs:simpleType></pre>

SCHEMA GAMING.XSD

Properties

attributeFormDefault:	unqualified
elementFormDefault:	qualified
targetNamespace:	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming

Elements

[Gaming-content-codes](#)
[Gaming-content-code](#)
[Gaming-content-qualifier](#)
[Gaming-property](#)
[Gaming-event](#)
[event-metadata](#)
[event-stats](#)
[event-sponsor](#)
[site](#)
[site-metadata](#)
[site-stats](#)
[team](#)
[team-metadata](#)
[home-location](#)
[team-stats](#)
[sub-score](#)
[sub-score-attempts](#)
[penalty-stats](#)
[outcome-totals](#)
[event-record](#)
[rank](#)
[rating](#)
[affiliation](#)
[player](#)
[player-metadata](#)
[career-phase](#)
[name](#)

Complex Types

Simple Types

[genericType](#)
[genericKeyType](#)
[genericKeyListType](#)
[position.Common](#)
[dateTime.Common](#)
[duration.Common](#)
[statsCoverage.Core](#)
[teamCoverage.Core](#)
[dateCoverageType.Core](#)
[durationScope.Core](#)
[competitionScope.Core](#)
[alignmentScope.Core](#)
[recordMakingScope.Core](#)
[codeType.Core](#)
[eventStyle.Core](#)
[eventStatus.Core](#)
[postponementStatus.Core](#)
[phaseStatus.Core](#)
[locationType.Core](#)
[status.Core](#)
[health.Core](#)
[gender.Core](#)
[participantCount.Core](#)
[professionalStatus.Core](#)
[specialGroup.Core](#)
[specialNeeds.Core](#)
[siteStyle.Core](#)

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[associate-metadata](#)
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[official](#)
[official-metadata](#)
[official-stats](#)
[highlight](#)
[award](#)
[event-actions](#)

[siteSurface.Core](#)
[scoreUnits.Core](#)
[resultEffect.Core](#)
[awardType.Core](#)
[bodySide.Core](#)

complexType **Gaming-content-codes**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="Gaming-content-codes"> <complexType> <sequence minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-content-code"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **Gaming-content-code**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="Gaming-content-code"> <complexType> <sequence minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-content-qualifier"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="code-type" type="Gamingml:codeType.Core" use="required"> </attribute> <attribute name="code-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="code-source" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="code-name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **Gaming-content-qualifier**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="Gaming-content-qualifier"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="gender" type="Gamingml:gender.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="participant-count" type="Gamingml:participantCount.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="professional-status" type="Gamingml:professionalStatus.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="special-group" type="Gamingml:specialGroup.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="minimum-age" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="maximum-age" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="special-needs" type="Gamingml:specialNeeds.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **Gaming-property**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="Gaming-property"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="formal-name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="vocabulary" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="scheme" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="value" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </pre>

	<pre> <attribute name="allowed-values" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
--	--

complexType **Gaming-event**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="Gaming-event"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:event-metadata" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:event-stats" minOccurs="0"/> <choice> <element ref="Gamingml:team" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:player" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </choice> <element ref="Gamingml:officials" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:event-actions" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:highlight" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:award" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-event" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </pre>

	</element>
--	------------

complexType **event-metadata**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="event-metadata"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-content-codes" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:eventMetadataSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:event-sponsor" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:site" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:siteAttributes"/> <attribute name="event-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-source" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-recurring-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-recurring-name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-style" type="Gamingml:eventStyle.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-number" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </pre>

	<pre> <attribute name="event-status" type="Gamingml:eventStatus.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-status-reason" type="Gamingml:genericType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-status-note" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-of-day" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="events-day-total" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="postponement-status" type="Gamingml:postponementStatus.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="postponement-note" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="start-date-time" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="start-weekday" use="optional"> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="sunday"/> <enumeration value="monday"/> <enumeration value="tuesday"/> <enumeration value="wednesday"/> <enumeration value="thursday"/> <enumeration value="friday"/> <enumeration value="saturday"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> <attribute name="end-date-time" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="end-weekday" use="optional"> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="sunday"/> <enumeration value="monday"/> <enumeration value="tuesday"/> <enumeration value="wednesday"/> <enumeration value="thursday"/> <enumeration value="friday"/> <enumeration value="saturday"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> <attribute name="heat-number" type="string" use="optional"> </pre>
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	<pre> </attribute> <attribute name="duration" type="Gamingml:duration.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="time-certainty" use="optional"> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="certain"/> <enumeration value="to-be-announced"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> <attribute name="season-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="season-type" type="Gamingml:seasonType.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="series-index" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="event-outcome-type" use="optional"> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="regular"/> <enumeration value="overtime"/> <enumeration value="shootout"/> <enumeration value="extra-time"/> <enumeration value="random"/> <enumeration value="authority-decision"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
--	---

complexType event-stats

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="event-stats"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:eventStatsSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> </sequence> </complexType> </element> </pre>

	<pre> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>
--	--

complexType **event-sponsor**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="event-sponsor"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="type" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="name" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **site**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="site"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:site-metadata"/> <element ref="Gamingml:site-stats" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **site-metadata**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <element name="site-metadata"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:name" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:home-location" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-content-code" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="site-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="site-source" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="capacity" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="style" type="Gamingml:siteStyle.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="surface" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="shape" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="incline" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="length" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="length-units" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="type" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="home-page-url" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **site-stats**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="site-stats"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attribute name="alignment" use="optional"> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="home"/> <enumeration value="neutral"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> <attribute name="attendance" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="attendance-average" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="temperature" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="temperature-units" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="weather-code" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="weather-label" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="weather-wind" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="weather-prediction" type="Gamingml:weatherPrediction.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="probability-of-precipitation" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **team**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <element name="team"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:team-metadata"/> <element ref="Gamingml:team-stats" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:player" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:associate" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:affiliation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:site" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **team-metadata**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <element name="team-metadata"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:name" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:site" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:home-location" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-content-code" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:teamMetadataSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="team-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="team-source" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="alignment" use="optional"/> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="home"/> <enumeration value="away"/> <enumeration value="none"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> <attribute name="team-idref" type="IDREF" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="home-page-url" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="round-position" type="string" use="optional"/> </element> </pre>

	<pre> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
--	---

complexType **home-location**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="home-location"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attribute name="location-type" type="Gamingml:locationType.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="street-number" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="street" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="street-prefix" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="street-suffix" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="suite" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="floor" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="building" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="city" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="county" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="area" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="state" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="country" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="postal-code" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="timezone" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="latitude" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="longitude" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </pre>

	<code></complexType></code> <code></element></code>
--	--

complexType **team-stats**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="team-stats"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:sub-score" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:sub-score-attempts" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:penalty-stats" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:outcome-totals" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:highlight" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:award" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:event-record" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> </complexType> </pre>

	<pre> <element ref="Gamingml:rank" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:rating" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:teamStatsSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:statAttributes"/> <attribute name="events-played" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="time-played-total" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="standing-points" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="games-back" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="streak" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
--	---

complexType sub-score

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="sub-score"> <complexType> <attribute name="period-value" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="score" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="sub-score-type" type="Gamingml:genericType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="sub-score-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="sub-score-name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="rank" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="total-score" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **sub-score-attempts**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="sub-score-attempts"> <complexType> <attribute name="period-value" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="score-attempts" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **penalty-stats**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="penalty-stats"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="type" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="count" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="value" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **outcome-totals**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="outcome-totals"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attribute name="wins" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="losses" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="ties" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="undecideds" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="winning-percentage" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

	<pre> <attribute name="points-scored-for" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="points-scored-against" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="points-difference" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="standing-points" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="standing-points-against" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="streak-type" use="optional"> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="win"/> <enumeration value="loss"/> <enumeration value="tie"/> <enumeration value="score"/> <enumeration value="assist"/> <enumeration value="point"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> <attribute name="streak-duration" type="Gamingml:duration.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="streak-total" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="streak-start" type="Gamingml:dateTime.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="streak-end" type="Gamingml:dateTime.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="events-played" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="events-remaining" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="games-back" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="losses-overtime" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
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complexType **event-record**

diagram	
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namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="event-record"> <complexType> <attribute name="type" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="previous-record" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType rank

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="rank"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attribute name="type" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="issuer" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="value" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="value-previous" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType rating

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="rating"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="rating-type" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="rating-issuer" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="rating-value" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="rating-maximum" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **affiliation**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="affiliation"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attribute name="membership-idref" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="membership-type" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="membership-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="membership-name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **player**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="player"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:player-metadata"/> <element ref="Gamingml:player-stats" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:associate" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:affiliation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **player-metadata**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <element name="player-metadata"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:name" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:home-location" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:career-phase" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:injury-phase" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:playerMetadataSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="player-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"/> <attribute name="player-source" type="string" use="optional"/> <attribute name="team-idref" type="string" use="optional"/> <attribute name="team-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"/> <attribute name="status" type="Gamingml:status.Core" use="optional"/> <attribute name="date-of-birth" type="string" use="optional"/> <attribute name="date-of-death" type="string" use="optional"/> <attribute name="height" type="string" use="optional"/> </complexType> </pre>

	<pre> </attribute> <attribute name="weight" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="position-regular" type="Gamingml:position.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="position-event" type="Gamingml:position.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="position-depth" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="lineup-slot" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="lineup-slot-sequence" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="position-source" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="health" type="Gamingml:health.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="scratch-reason" type="Gamingml:health.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="uniform-number" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="home-page-url" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="gender" use="optional"> <simpleType> <restriction base="string"> <enumeration value="male"/> <enumeration value="female"/> </restriction> </simpleType> </attribute> <attribute name="nationality" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="round-position" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
--	---

complexType career-phase

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre><element name="career-phase"> <complexType></pre>

	<pre> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="phase-type" type="Gamingml:phaseType.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="start-date" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="end-date" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="duration" type="Gamingml:duration.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="subphase-type" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="phase-status" type="Gamingml:phaseStatus.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="phase-caliber" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="phase-caliber-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="entry-reason" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="selection-level" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="selection-sublevel" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="selection-overall" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="exit-reason" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="weight" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="position-regular" type="Gamingml:position.Common" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="position-depth" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="uniform-number" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
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complexType **name**

diagram	name
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="name"> <complexType mixed="true"> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="role" type="Gamingml:genericKeyListType"/> <attribute name="part" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType"/> <attribute name="full" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="first" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="middle" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="last" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="nickname" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="prefix" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="suffix" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="abbreviation" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="language" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **player-stats**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <element name="player-stats"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:sub-score" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:sub-score-attempts" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:penalty-stats" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:outcome-totals" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:highlight" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:award" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:event-record" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:rank" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:rating" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:playerStatsSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </pre>

	<pre> maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:coverageAttributes"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:statAttributes"/> <attribute name="time-played-event" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="time-played-total" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="time-played-event-average" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="events-played" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="events-started" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
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complexType **associate**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="associate"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:associate-metadata"/> <element ref="Gamingml:associate-stats" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:affiliation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **associate-metadata**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <element name="associate-metadata"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:name" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:home-location" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:associateMetadataSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="associate-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="associate-source" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="position" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> <attribute name="position-source" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **associate-stats**

<p>diagram</p>	
<p>namespace</p>	<p>http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming</p>
<p>source</p>	<pre> <element name="associate-stats"> <complexType> <sequence> </pre>

	<pre> <element ref="Gamingml:rating" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:outcome-totals" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:associateStatsSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="points" type="string" use="optional"/> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>
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complexType **officials**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="officials"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:official" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **official**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="official"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:official-metadata"/> <element ref="Gamingml:official-stats" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:affiliation" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **official-metadata**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="official-metadata"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:name" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <element ref="Gamingml:home-location" minOccurs="0"/> <element ref="Gamingml:Gaming-property" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> <group ref="Gamingml:officialMetadataSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> <attribute name="official-key" type="Gamingml:genericKeyType" use="optional"/> <attribute name="official-source" type="string" use="optional"/> <attribute name="position" type="string" use="optional"/> <attribute name="position-source" type="string" use="optional"/> <attribute name="uniform-number" type="string" use="optional"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **official-stats**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="official-stats"> <complexType> <sequence> <element ref="Gamingml:rating" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> </complexType> </element> </pre>

	<pre> <group ref="Gamingml:officialStatsSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>
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complexType **highlight**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="highlight"> <complexType mixed="true"> <sequence> <any processContents="lax" minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/> </sequence> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:commonAttributes"/> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **award**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre> <element name="award"> <complexType> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:commonAttributes"/> <attribute name="award-type" type="Gamingml:awardType.Core" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="name" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="player-or-team-idref" type="IDREF" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="total" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="place" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="value" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> <attribute name="currency" type="string" use="optional"> </attribute> </complexType> </element> </pre>

complexType **event-actions**

diagram	
namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
source	<pre><element name="event-actions"> <complexType> <group ref="Gamingml:eventActionsSpecific" minOccurs="0"/> <attributeGroup ref="Gamingml:globalAttributes"/> </complexType> </element></pre>

simpleType **genericType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="genericType"> <restriction base="string"> <pattern value="[^\s:]+:[^\s]+"/> </restriction> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **genericKeyType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="genericKeyType"> <restriction base="string"> <pattern value="[^\s:]+:[^\s]+"/> </restriction> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **genericKeyListType**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="genericKeyListType"> <list itemType="Gamingml:genericKeyType"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **position.Common**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="position.Common"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **dateTime.Common**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="dateTime.Common"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **duration.Common**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="duration.Common"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **statsCoverage.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="statsCoverage.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **teamCoverage.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="teamCoverage.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **dateCoverageType.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="dateCoverageType.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **durationScope.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="durationScope.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **competitionScope.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
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type	string
source	<simpleType name="competitionScope.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **alignmentScope.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="alignmentScope.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **recordMakingScope.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="recordMakingScope.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **codeType.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="codeType.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **eventStyle.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="eventStyle.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **eventStatus.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="eventStatus.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **postponementStatus.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="postponementStatus.Core">

	<pre><restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>
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simpleType **phaseStatus.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="phaseStatus.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **locationType.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="locationType.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **status.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="status.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **health.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="health.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **phaseType.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="phaseType.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **gender.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<pre><simpleType name="gender.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType></pre>

simpleType **participantCount.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="participantCount.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **professionalStatus.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="professionalStatus.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **specialGroup.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="specialGroup.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **specialNeeds.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="specialNeeds.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **siteStyle.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="siteStyle.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **siteSurface.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="siteSurface.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **scoreUnits.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="scoreUnits.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **resultEffect.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="resultEffect.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **awardType.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="awardType.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>

simpleType **bodySide.Core**

namespace	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/XMLSchema/v1.0/Gaming
type	string
source	<simpleType name="bodySide.Core"> <restriction base="string"/> </simpleType>